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SUN-PROTECTIVE BEHAVIORS IN PATIENTS WITH MELASMA

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By

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ABSTRACT

Sun exposure is the greatest triggering factor in melasma, yet few studies investigate how patients with melasma practice sun-protective behaviors such as avoiding sun exposure, seeking shade, and using sunscreen correctly. The purpose of this project was to gain perspective about barriers to sun-protective behaviors of patients with melasma. A mixed-methods design was utilized to investigate sun-protective behaviors through a demographic questionnaire, Sun Exposure and Protection Index (SEPI) survey, and semi-structured interviews. Twenty-one participants completed the SEPI survey and 13 participants were interviewed. The majority of participants were 25-34 years (38%), Caucasian/White (57%), and had melasma for 3 or more years (84%). When asked how often they thought about their melasma, participants answered “always” (43%) and “often” (38%) most frequently. Regarding sunscreen reapplication, only five participants (23%) reapplied sunscreen every 2 hours as recommended. As time spent thinking about melasma increased, sunscreen SPF increased ($r_s = 0.44, p = .044$). As sunscreen reapplication increased, SEPI II Scores decreased ($r_s = -0.47, p = .030$). Interviews revealed a lack of knowledge and perceived risk regarding incidental sun exposures and proper sunscreen use. This study was limited by its small sample size of all female and mainly white, young adult participants which may be difficult to generalize to other populations. Patients with melasma would benefit from education that discusses how to

properly choose, apply, and reapply sunscreen and how to recognize and limit incidental sun exposure.

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BACKGROUND

Melasma is an acquired, chronic disorder, characterized by hyperpigmentation in sun-exposed areas of the skin, particularly the face (Handel, Miot, & Miot, 2014; Kwon, Hwang, Lee, & Park, 2016; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). Clinical manifestations of melasma typically include light brown to dark brown irregular patches on the centrofacial, malar, and mandibular regions of the skin (Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017; Sheth & Pandya, 2011a). Women of reproductive age with darker skin phenotypes are disproportionately affected by this condition (Handel et al., 2014; Lee, 2015; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017; Ortonne et al., 2009; Sheth & Pandya, 2011a). The etiology of melasma remains complex and unclear, although female sex hormones, genetics, inflammatory processes, and certain medications appear to play a role in its pathogenesis (Kwon et al., 2016; Lee, 2015; Ortonne et al., 2009; Sheth & Pandya, 2011a). Ultraviolet radiation (UVR) also initiates and exacerbates the condition (Kwon et al., 2016; Lee, 2015; Ortonne et al., 2009; Sheth & Pandya, 2011a). Sun exposure is considered the greatest triggering and exacerbating factor in melasma (Handel et al., 2014).

Significance of the Problem

Descriptions of melasma were first noted in the medical reports of Hippocrates (470-360 BC) in which he detailed hyperpigmentation made worse after exposure to sun, temperature changes, and inflammation (Handel et al., 2014). Although not a new condition, it has been difficult to estimate the prevalence of melasma globally, as few studies have randomly sampled the general population (Sheth & Pandya, 2011a). Epidemiological studies that have investigated cutaneous disorders show the prevalence

of melasma can range from 1% in the general population to up to 50% in higher-risk groups (Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). At a private practice in Orange County, California, 10-20% of patients present with complaints and a clinical history consistent with melasma.

Melasma continues to be a significant problem for patients and is associated with a negative impact on quality of life (Jiang, Akinseye, Tovar-Garza, & Pandya, 2018; Ikino, Nunes, Silva, Fröde, & Sens, 2015; Sheth & Pandya, 2011a). Because this condition typically occurs on the face, it is easily visible and a constant presence in everyday life, which contributes to its distressing impact on patients (Handel et al., 2014). Regardless of melasma severity, women with this condition were negatively impacted by their disease (Sheth & Pandya, 2011a). In addition to the physical and emotional cost associated with melasma, the financial costs are also significant. Management is often multifactorial and includes pharmacological topical creams, laser therapies, and avoidance of triggers, including sun-protective behaviors (Sheth & Pandya, 2011b). Due to its chronic nature, long-term treatments are often necessary and recurrence rates are high, leaving patients dissatisfied with care (Handel et al., 2014). As melasma is typically treated as a cosmetic concern, and treatments are not covered by insurance, the most cost-effective way of reducing melasma exacerbations is practicing sun-protective behaviors.

Problem Statement

There are a lack of studies identifying knowledge of sun-protective behaviors in patients with melasma. A systematic review of randomized controlled trial (RCT) on interventions for melasma found that all RCTs evaluated therapies to reduce pigment in melasma, but none looked at preventative measures such as use of sunscreen (Jutley,

Rajaratnam, Halpern, Salim, & Emmett, 2014). Jutley et al. (2014) concluded that it is important for patients with melasma to understand sun-protective concepts such as sun protection factor (SPF) and how often to apply sunscreen. A 2017 study identifying consumer knowledge of sunscreen in the general adult population found that participants had poor comprehension of sunscreen labels and only 2% of 711 participants applied sunscreen more than once daily (Chao, Sheu, Kong, Rademaker, & Kundu, 2017). Another study measuring sun-protective behaviors in patients with hyperpigmented cutaneous disorders, including melasma, found that although 67.5% of participants used some form of sunscreen, only 7.6% reapplied every 2 hours as recommended (Maymone et al., 2017). Little is known about how patients with melasma understand and practice sun-protective behaviors such as avoiding sun exposure, seeking shade, choosing appropriate sunscreen, and using sunscreen correctly. In our practice, patients with melasma are educated about sun protection on every visit, yet the majority of patients report they are not engaging in sun-protective behaviors consistently.

Purpose Statement

The goal of this scholarly project was to gain perspective about barriers to sun-protective behaviors of patients with melasma and develop evidence- and data-based practice recommendations for patient education. The objectives were to:

1. Investigate self-reported sun-protective behaviors in adult patients with melasma through use of the Sun Exposure and Protection Index (SEPI) survey.
2. Understand the experience of using sun-protective behaviors through semi-structured patient interviews.

3. Use findings to make recommendations that will better assist health care providers when providing patient education regarding sun-protective behaviors to patients with melasma.

Supportive Framework

The Health Promotion Model

The Health Promotion Model (HPM) and Transtheoretical Model (TTM) were used to organize and guide this project. The HPM was created by Nola Pender to help nurses explore factors and relationships that motivate individuals to engage in health behaviors (Pender, Murdaugh, & Parsons, 2011). These factors are considered when nurses provide behavioral counseling to promote healthy lifestyles and behaviors (Pender et al., 2011). Pender was influenced by three major theories when constructing the HPM: the Reciprocal Interaction World View, the Expectancy Value Theory, and the Social Cognitive Theory (Pender et al., 2011). The Reciprocal Interaction World View posits that humans are holistic beings, interacting with and shaping their environment to meet their individual needs and goals (Pender et al., 2011). The Expectancy Value Theory states that individuals will engage in goal-achieving activities if they perceive that the goal is both attainable and valued (Pender et al., 2011). The Social Cognitive Theory asserts that behaviors are influenced by interactions between thoughts, behaviors, and the environment, and for people to change their behavior, they must also change how they think (Pender et al., 2011).

Components and propositions of the health promotion model. The three major components of the HPM are: individual characteristics and experiences, behavior-specific cognitions and affect, and behavioral outcomes. Individual characteristics and

experiences are comprised of prior related behavior and personal factors, whereas behavior-specific cognitions and affect include perceived benefits or barriers to action, perceived self-efficacy, activity-related affect, and interpersonal and situational influences (McEwen and Wills, 2011; Pender et al., 2011). Behavioral outcomes focus on a commitment to a plan of action and balance of competing demands and preferences resulting in health-promoting behavior (McEwen and Wills, 2011; Pender et al., 2011).

Health-promoting behavior is influenced by an individual's previous behaviors and personal characteristics (Pender et al., 2011). An individual is more likely to engage in health-promoting behavior if they believe that behavior will lead to a valued outcome, and an individual is less likely to commit to a plan of action toward a behavior if perceived (or actual) barriers are present (Pender et al., 2011). Individuals are more likely to commit to a plan of action and perform a behavior if they have a positive attitude toward that behavior and have perceived self-efficacy in that behavior (Pender et al., 2011). Greater perceived self-efficacy combined with fewer perceived barriers increases the likelihood that the individual will commit to a plan of action (Pender et al., 2011).

Interpersonal influences, such as significant others, family, peers, and health care providers (HCPs), and situational influences in the external environment will impact the individual's commitment to and engagement in a behavior (Pender et al., 2011).

Interpersonal influences that model, expect, and support a behavior will increase the likelihood that the individual will commit to and engage in that behavior (Pender et al., 2011). A greater commitment to a plan of action will result in behavior that is maintained over time (Pender et al. 2011). Competing demands that require immediate attention or that appear more attractive will make a commitment to a plan of action less likely to

occur (Pender et al., 2011). Individuals can create incentives for health-promoting behaviors by modifying their thoughts, feelings, and external influences.

Figure 1. The Health Promotion Model. Reprinted from *Health Promotion in Nursing Practice* by N.J. Pender, C.L. Murdaugh, and M.A. Parsons, 2011, Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Education, Inc. © 2011.

Application of the health promotion model. First appearing in literature in 1982 and revised in 1996, the HPM has been used for over 27 years as a framework for nursing inquiry aimed at behavioral interventions (McEwen and Wills, 2011; Pender et al., 2011). The HPM was used to develop an interview guide that assessed the participant's understanding of sun-protection and sun-exposure behaviors. It is imperative for patients with melasma to practice sun-protective behaviors to delay or prevent melasma

exacerbations, yet the barriers to committing to sun-protective behaviors remain unclear. Once perceived barriers are identified, the HCP, a key source of interpersonal influence for the patient, can motivate the patient to engage in sun-protective behaviors more consistently.

The Transtheoretical Model

The Transtheoretical Model (TTM) was developed by James Prochaska and Carlo DiClemente to describe the process of intentional behavioral change. The process of behavior change is described through a series of stages with each stage representing a different principle (Prochaska et al., 1992). The six stages of change are: precontemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, maintenance, and termination (Prochaska et al., 1992). During precontemplation, the individual has no intention to change the behavior in the immediate future and may not be aware that a behavioral problem exists (Prochaska et al., 1992). In the contemplation stage, the individual is aware a problem exists, but has not committed to a plan to address the problem (Prochaska et al., 1992). During the next stage, preparation, the individual is intending to take action with behavioral change in the next 30 days (Prochaska et al., 1992). The individual adjusts his or her behavior during the action stage, which lasts around six months and leads into the maintenance stage, when the individual continues to prevent relapsing into prior behaviors and can last six months to five years (Prochaska et al., 1992). Once the individual has zero temptation to return to previous behaviors, he or she has reached the termination stage (Prochaska et al., 1992). The stages of change are referred to in a spiral pattern, as the individual may relapse into previous behaviors and then return to a previous stage (Prochaska et al., 1992).

*Figure 2. A Spiral Model of the Stages of Change. Reprinted from “In search of how people change,” by J.O. Prochaska, C.C. DiClemente, and J.C. Norcross, 1992, *American Psychology*, 47(9), p. 1104. © 1992.*

Application of the transtheoretical model. The TTM has been used extensively to evaluate addictive behaviors and has been used more recently to evaluate sun-protective behaviors in various populations (Santiago-Rivas et al., 2013; Santiago-Rivas et al., 2015; Yin et al., 2014; Babbin et al., 2015; Brick et al., 2016; Yusufov et al., 2016; Sillice et al., 2018). The TTM was part of the Sun Exposure and Protection Index (SEPI) survey tool that assessed the participant’s readiness to change or engage in sun-protective behaviors. Determining the patient’s TTM stage enables HCPs to design interventions that can motivate the individual to transition from one stage to another.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A systematic review of literature was performed to identify recent studies that investigated sun-protective behaviors in patients with melasma. Studies that were five years or older were included if they were referenced multiple times by recent authors. Electronic databases utilized were: Academic Search Complete, Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), Google Scholar, PsychINFO, PubMed (NLM), and Science Direct. Search terms were: “melasma” or “melanosis” which was cross-referenced using Boolean strategy using AND and OR with keywords “sun-protective behaviors,” “sun protection,” and “sunscreen.” As only two studies directly measured sun-protective behaviors in patients with melasma, the university librarian was consulted to confirm that the search strategy was performed correctly. The majority of articles found relevant to melasma were related to treatment options, such as topical creams, oral medications, and laser modalities. Minimal attention had been given to preventative measures such as sun-protective behaviors (Appendix A).

To find relevant studies, the search was expanded to identify studies investigating sun-protective behaviors in patients with or at high risk for skin cancer, as this is another condition in which prolonged sun-exposure can have detrimental effects. Articles were excluded if sample populations were outside of the U.S. and younger than 18 years of age or if access to the full report was not possible. Other scholarly sources reviewed were: the American Academy of Dermatology (AAD), the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ), the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), the National Cancer Institute (NCI), the National Guideline Clearinghouse (NGC), and the National Health Interview Survey (NHIS) to assess for trends, guidelines, and recommendations

regarding sun-protective behaviors. The literature search strategy is detailed in Appendix B.

The first section of this literature review will provide a summary of the epidemiology, etiology, diagnosis, and management of melasma. The second section will synthesize the literature regarding sun-protective behaviors in patients with melasma and those with or at high risk for skin cancer. The Health Promotion Model (HPM) will be discussed as it applies to the studies examined.

Melasma

Epidemiology and Etiology

Melasma is an acquired disorder of hyperpigmentation and can occur on various areas of the body, but most commonly develops on the centrofacial, malar, and mandibular areas of the face (Sheth & Pandya, 2011a; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). Melasma can occur in all skin types and ethnic groups, but higher prevalence has been reported in darker skin phenotypes, specifically East Asian, Indian, Pakistani, Middle Eastern and Mediterranean-African population groups (Handel et al., 2014; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). Prevalence is estimated to be as low as 1% in the general population and up to 50% in higher-risk groups, depending on the prevalence of darker skin populations and levels of UV exposure in various geographic locations (Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). One study in Texas reported that 8.2% of 500 Latino women surveyed had self-reported melasma (Werlinger et al., 2007) while a second study reported 15.5% of Arab-American women living in Michigan had self-reported melasma (El-Essawi et al., 2007).

The etiology of melasma is complex and multifactorial. Melasma predominately affects women of reproductive age. The true age of onset is unknown but estimated to be between 20 and 30 years of age (Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). To further investigate causative factors for melasma development, Ortonne et al. (2009) designed a 40-item questionnaire completed by a global sample of 324 women that had been treated for melasma and found 48% had a family history of melasma (97% of which were in a first-degree relative) and tended to have darker skin (90% had types III-IV). Twenty-nine percent had melasma prior to pregnancy, 26% developed melasma during pregnancy, and 42% developed melasma following pregnancy (Ortonne et al., 2009). The risk of onset during pregnancy was associated with increased age and time spent outdoors (Ortonne et al., 2009). It is well documented that melasma is more common in women with a history of sun exposure, suggesting that UV light triggers and exacerbates the condition (Sheth & Pandya, 2011a; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017).

Melasma is characterized by hyperpigmentation of the skin, but other abnormalities of the skin are observed, including changes in the basement membrane, increased vascularization, and increased number of mast cells (Kwon et al., 2016). Previous studies have also noted that melanocytes in patients with melasma are more biologically active (Handel et al., 2014; Sheth & Pandya 2011b). It is estimated that as high as 83 to 93% of melasma patients also have solar elastosis, an accumulation of abnormal elastic tissue from prolonged sun exposure, further providing evidence that sun exposure plays a role in melasma development (Kwon et al., 2016). Ultraviolet A (UVA) exposure can cause immediate skin darkening due to redistribution of pre-existing melanin and usually fades after two hours; however, higher doses can lead to pigment

darkening that lasted 24 hours (Sheth & Pandya, 2011b). Ultraviolet B (UVB) radiation induces melanocyte proliferation and migration, leading to cytokine production and melanogenesis (Sheth & Pandya, 2011b; Kwon et al., 2016). Less common causes of melasma include thyroid disorders, phototoxic medications, and cosmetics (Sheth & Pandya, 2011).

Diagnosis and Management

Melasma is typically diagnosed in a patient who presents with symmetric hyperpigmentation with irregular borders on the face and with a clinical history suggestive of melasma (Sheth & Pandya, 2011b; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). Epidermal and dermal melasma can be differentiated through use of a Wood's lamp, a device used to detect pigmentary disorders of the skin (Sheth & Pandya, 2011a; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). While other diagnostic tools exist, such as histology studies, melasma is mainly diagnosed clinically.

Topical creams, oral medications, and procedural treatments such as light-based and laser modalities and microneedling are used to treat melasma (Sheth & Pandya, 2011b; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). Treatments differ depending on what area of melasma pathogenesis they are targeting, such as photodamage, pigmentation, inflammation, and vascularity (Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). First-line treatments for melasma are topical therapies aimed at disrupting pigment production and using sun-protective measures (Sheth & Pandya, 2011b; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). Both UVA and UVB can lead to melanin synthesis and sunscreens should protect against both UVA and UVB spectrums (Sheth & Pandya, 2011b). It is now documented that visible light (light on the visible spectrum that is detected by the human eye) can also induce

pigmentation and protection against both UV and visible light is recommended (Bourkari et al., 2015). Patients with melasma should be instructed to reapply sunscreen frequently (at least every two hours is recommended) and engage in other sun-protective behaviors such as seeking shade and wearing protective clothing and hats (Sheth & Pandya, 2011b).

Hydroquinone (HQ) cream is the most common topical agent prescribed for melasma. HQ inhibits tyrosinase, preventing melanin production, and is usually used in combination with other creams (Sheth & Pandya, 2011b; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). Corticosteroid topical creams also suppress melanin production and are often prescribed in combination with HQ (Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). Topical retinoid creams increase keratinocyte turnover, decrease melanin synthesis, and allow greater penetration of other active ingredients (Sheth & Pandya, 2011b; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). Other topical treatments include kojic acid, azelaic acid, and ascorbic acid (Sheth & Pandya, 2011b). Combination therapies are recommended as no single therapy has been shown to benefit all patients with melasma (Jutley et al., 2014; Sheth & Pandya, 2011b). Combined HQ, tretinoin, and steroid creams appear most effective at controlling melasma symptoms (Jutley et al., 2014; Sheth & Pandya, 2011b). A review of laser and light-based therapies in melasma found that intense pulse light (IPL), low fluence Q-switched lasers, and non-ablative fractionated lasers were most commonly used to treat melasma and regardless of modality used, long-term posttreatment maintenance was necessary to slow recurrence (Trivedi et al., 2017).

Tools for Outcome Measurements

Outcome measurements are necessary for the patient and clinician to determine if current treatment modalities are improving symptoms. Four tools are used: the Melasma

Area and Severity Index (MASI), the modified MASI (mMASI), the Melasma Severity Score (MSS), and the Melasma Quality of Life (MelasQoL). The MASI is used to measure baseline and outcome measures for patients with melasma and is scored on three subjective factors: area of involvement (forehead, malar, and chin regions), darkness, and homogeneity (Sheth & Pandya, 2011a; Ogbechie-Godec & Elbuluk, 2017). Five dermatologists and one dermatology resident were recruited along with 21 patients with mild to severe melasma to determine the reliability and validity of the MASI score. To determine intrarater and interrater reliability, the clinicians rated the 21 patients over a period of two days. Intrarater reliability was assessed through weighted kappa statistics which compared MASI scores on patients from day one to day two (Pandya et al., 2011). Results showed moderate agreement for area, darkness, and homogeneity values for the forehead and darkness values for the malar regions (Pandya et al., 2011). Interrater reliability was assessed using Spearman rank order correlations, which compared MASI darkness ratings between raters on both days (Pandya et al., 2011). The average score was greater than 0.4, which translated to moderate agreement between raters (Pandya et al., 2011). Correlation scores increased from day one to day two, meeting criterion for good reliability for all areas except the chin (Pandya et al., 2011). Validation was achieved by comparing MASI scores to the MSS on both days. Spearman correlation for MASI scores versus MSS scores displayed good agreement for all raters on both days (Pandya et al., 2011). Pandya et al., (2011) suggested using mMASI which eliminates homogeneity from the calculation (due to decreased interrater reliability).

The MSS, has four grades of severity: clear, mild, moderate, and severe with clear or mild being ideal outcome scores (Rodrigues et al., 2016). The MSS is used to provide

a global score that is easy to use for both clinicians and patients and used as an outcome measurement (Rodrigues et al., 2016), Rodrigues et al. (2016) sought to correlate mMASI ranges into MSS categories so that clinicians interpret melasma studies and identify melasma patients with more ease. Seventy-nine patients were scored using the MASI, mMASI, and MSS tools. Results of MSS to the MASI and mMASI were compared using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) statistics. The authors were able to show mMASI ranges correspond to MSS levels (Rodrigues et al., 2016). The MASI and the mMASI are reliable and validated tools that can be used to measure melasma outcomes in the clinical setting (Pandya et al., 2011; Rodrigues et al., 2016).

The MelasQoL is a validated scale that can help provide outcome measurements related to QoL. The scale was developed by choosing items from the SKINDEX-16 scale and a skin discoloration questionnaire that were melasma-specific HRQoL (Balkrishnan et al., 2003). A sample of 102 women with melasma were surveyed with well-known QoL dermatology scales and the MelasQoL scale. Using Cronbach's α and Ferguson Index statistics, the psychometric properties of the MelasQoL scale were comparable to the other QoL scales, making it a valid instrument (Balkrishnan et al., 2003). When validating the tool, Balkrishnan et al. found the three life domains most affected were social life, recreation and leisure, and emotional well-being (2003).

Much is known about the epidemiology, etiology, diagnosis, and treatment of melasma, yet it continues to be a condition that is poorly managed, leaving patients dissatisfied with care. Women of reproductive age continue to be disproportionately affected by melasma and require chronic and costly treatments to stabilize the condition and prevent exacerbations. Treatment options are not covered by insurance and consist of

costly topical medications and expensive laser or light-based modalities. More attention must be placed on affordable preventative measures, such as the importance of practicing sun-protective behaviors. After conducting an extensive systematic review of randomized controlled trials (RCTs) on interventions for melasma, Jutley et al. (2014) concluded that studies often recommend sun protection, yet there are no RCTs that investigate sun-protection factor, dosing, and frequency of application.

Sun-Protective Behaviors

Examples of sun-protective behaviors are using sunscreen (including correct SPF and reapplication), seeking shade, and wearing protective clothing (such as long sleeves and wide-brimmed hats). The two studies that investigate sun-protective behaviors in patients with melasma are summarized below.

Sun-Protective Behaviors in Patients with Melasma

Maymone et al. (2017) examined sun-protective behaviors in patients with hyperpigmentation disorders, including melasma. Data was obtained using a self-developed survey that included questions about demographics, sunscreen use, and other sun protective measures, and a clinical evaluation by a trained dermatologist for skin-typing. Close to 40% of participants had melasma, and of those, 55% attributed their condition to sun exposure. Compared to other disorders of pigmentation, patients with melasma were more likely to use sunscreen and seek shade. Overall 67.5% of all participants reported using sunscreen, but only 7.6% reapplied every 2 hours. Maymone et al. (2017) concluded that even for motivated patients, sun protective education is needed.

Boukari et al. (2015) sought to evaluate protective properties of UVA/UVB protective sunscreens that also protected against shorter wavelengths of visible light compared with UVA/UVB sunscreens with no visible light protection in patients with melasma. Forty women were randomized into 2 groups: with one group receiving UVA/UVB protective sunscreen with additional visible light protection and the other group receiving regular UVA/UVB sunscreen protection. MASI scores and standardized photos were taken before treatment as a baseline measurement and again 6 months after the intervention. MASI scores increased in the group without visible light protection, indicating that the sunscreen with additional visible light protection would benefit patients with melasma (Boukari et al., 2015). The study was less about sun-protective behaviors and more about sunscreen choice, although participants were instructed how to correctly apply sunscreen and the importance of applying every 2 hours with sun exposure.

A common theme in both studies was that patients would adhere to sun-protective behaviors when provided with the right tools (education and sunscreen). Patients were more likely to engage in sun-protective behaviors in the Maymone et al. (2017) study because over half (55%) had the knowledge that sun exposure made their condition worse. The Boukari et al. (2015) study could not have been completed without the participants' adherence to sun-protective behaviors (in this case sunscreen application). Both studies support the HPM, in that they show how individuals are more likely to engage in health-promoting behavior (sunscreen use) if they believe that behavior will lead to a valued outcome (improvement in melasma symptoms).

Sun-Protective Behaviors in Patients with or at Risk for Skin Cancer

Several themes emerged when examining the literature regarding sun-protective behaviors and skin cancer: a) increased knowledge and greater perceived self-efficacy will contribute to increased engagement in sun-protective behaviors, b) a lack of education and perceived risk as well as perceived barriers will contribute to decreased and/or inconsistent sun-protective behaviors, c) personalized interventions and support from HCPs will improve adherence to sun-protective behaviors, and d) technology-based interventions are only useful if they are actively used.

Increased knowledge and greater perceived self-efficacy will contribute to increased engagement in sun-protective behaviors. Smith et al. (2018) aimed to assess the level of education and personal practices of sun-protective behaviors in medical students with varying levels of education. Medical students with greater knowledge of dermatology and further along in their education were significantly more likely to have used sun protection, leading authors to conclude increasing education would increase sun-protective behaviors (Smith et al., 2018). This is similar to Maymone et al.'s (2017) finding that melasma patients that were educated regarding exacerbating effects of sun exposure were more likely to use sunscreen and seek shade. Kamimura et al. (2015) examined sun-protective behaviors and their association with self-efficacy, susceptibility, and skin cancer awareness in low-income patients. Study results showed increased levels of self-efficacy were associated with increased levels of sunscreen use and increased levels of awareness were associated with increased levels of sunscreen use, seeking shade, and wearing sun-protective clothing (Kamimura et al., 2015).

Some studies employed educational interventions to determine their effect on behavior. Even when the educational interventions were brief, they were associated with a positive impact on sun-protective behaviors. Bagatti et al. (2016) investigated the effect of an educational intervention on knowledge, behavior, and attitudes of female college athletes regarding melanoma. Post-intervention, participants were more likely to apply sunscreen, check their skin for moles, and see a HCP (Bagatti et al., 2016). In a study involving operating engineers at risk for skin cancer, Lee et al. (2014) found 84% of participants expressed they intended to use sunscreen after a 30-minute PowerPoint presentation regarding sun protection. In another study investigating sun protection in adult Hispanics at risk for skin cancer, participants had greater knowledge of skin cancer and perceived risk after a brief educational film (Hernandez et al., 2014).

These studies suggest that increased knowledge and perceived self-efficacy will contribute to engagement in sun-protective behaviors. This is aligned with two HPM propositions. An individual is more likely to engage in health-promoting behavior if they believe that behavior will lead to a valued outcome (decreased risk of skin cancer), and greater perceived self-efficacy increases the likelihood that the individual will commit to a plan of action (using sunscreen, seeking shade, and wearing protective clothing). Some of the studies also highlighted another important concept of the HPM regarding interpersonal influences. Interpersonal influences, such as significant others, family, peers, and health care providers (HCPs), and situational influences in the external environment will impact the individual's commitment to and engagement in a behavior (Pender et al., 2011). In a study assessing sun-protective behaviors in college students, authors found that students who were concerned about sun exposure were more likely to

have parents that were worried about sun exposure and had a history of engaging in sun-protective behaviors (Yockey et al., 2017). In another study, supervisors that formally or informally encouraged sun protection were the most significant influence of sun protective behaviors for Latino day laborers (Boyas & Nahar, 2018). A study investigating sunscreen use before and after organ transplantation found that pretransplantation advice given by HCPs significantly impacted post-transplantation sun-protective behaviors (Mihalik et al., 2013).

Lack of perceived risks, lack of knowledge, and perceived barriers will lead to decreased and/or inconsistent sun-protective behaviors. Jacobsen et al. (2016) examined skin cancer prevention and educational needs among uninsured, minority, and immigrant communities in a large, free, medical clinic in Florida. Nearly half (44.3%) had never conducted a self-skin examination, 24.5% had never heard of skin cancer, 20.7% believed that people with darker skin could not get skin cancer (Jacobsen et al., 2016). Inconsistent and low sunscreen use was reported in 75.7% and reasons for not using sunscreen included being too hot and forgetting to use it (Jacobsen et al., 2016). Jacobsen et al. (2016) concluded that there was still a belief that dark-skinned individuals are protected from skin cancer and main barriers to skin cancer prevention were lack of knowledge. This lack of perceived risk was highlighted in other studies. In an interview of Hispanic women, only 48% believed they were at risk for skin cancer and 38% reported not using any sunscreen; out of those that did use sunscreen, only three participants applied sunscreen more than once during the day (Hernandez et al., 2014). Skin cancer is less common in Hispanic populations, but when diagnosed, it is at an

advanced stage due to lower risk perception and lower engagement in sun-protective behaviors (Hernandez et al., 2014).

Even in those with greater perceived risk, additional education is still needed. Fischer et al. (2016) examined whether those with previous nonmelanoma skin cancer (NMSC) engaged in better protection than those without a history of skin cancer. Participants that had previous NMSC had higher rates of using shade, wearing long sleeves, wearing wide-brimmed hats, and sunscreen than those without history of NMSC. Interestingly, those with previous NMSC did not have lower sunburn odds and sunburn was inversely related to age (recent sunburns reported in ages 18-39 years), sun avoidance, and seeking shade, but not sunscreen. Fisher et al. (2016) concluded that even motivated individuals (those with NMSC) could benefit from additional education with an emphasis on shade and sun avoidance in addition to sunscreen, especially in younger adults. The concept that additional education is needed even in those with a history of skin cancer is highlighted in another study. When investigating the sun-protective behaviors of patients with or at risk of skin cancer, while in vehicles, Kim et al. (2013) found that the majority of participants falsely believed that they did not need sun-protection while driving. Similarly, a study that evaluated attitudes and behaviors of outdoor college athletes at risk for skin cancer found a majority of athletes lacked knowledge about skin cancer in general, and 83% thought tanning beds improved one's health (Hobbs et al., 2014). The majority of participants had low levels of sun-protective behavior and less than 25% used sunscreen during practice or at other times when outdoors (Hobbs et al., 2014).

Perceived barriers can lead to decreased and inconsistent sun-protective behaviors. When assessing skin cancer knowledge, health beliefs, and sun protective behaviors in state park workers, Nahar et al. (2014) found that the majority of participants believed skin cancer was a serious disease, but only a minority believed they were at increased risk for skin cancer. Participants also reported low levels of sun-protective behaviors and forgetting to use, being inconvenient, and being too hot to wear as barriers to using sun protection, which were similar to previous findings of barriers to use in landscapers (Nahar et al., 2013; Nahar et al., 2014). Forgetting to use sunscreen was seen as a barrier in other studies as well. While investigating sun protection in young women at risk for skin cancer, authors found that forgetfulness and assuming protection was not needed during cloudy or cool weather were the most common barriers when using sun protection (Auerbach et al., 2018). Hay et al. (2017) investigated consistency of sun protection practices in first-degree relatives (FDR) of patients with melanoma that were seen at a large, urban cancer center in New York. Results showed 61% of participants used sunscreen inconsistently; reasons for not using sunscreen included not having adequate time to apply it and not using it when it was cloudy outside. Participants were more likely to seek shade when the weather was hot and uncomfortable and when it was conveniently available. Hay et al. (2017) concluded that understanding factors that drive choices will lead to developments that promote sun protection.

These studies show how a lack of perceived risk, lack of education, and perceived barriers can lead to decreased and inconsistent sun-protective behaviors. These concepts are aligned with the following propositions of the HPM: an individual is more likely to engage in health-promoting behavior if they believe that behavior will lead to a valued

outcome, an individual is less likely to commit to a plan of action if perceived (or actual) barriers are present, and situational influences in the external environment will impact the individual's commitment to and engagement in a behavior (Pender et al., 2011).

Educating patients on the importance of sun-protection and the risks associated with sun-exposure may lead to increased engagement in sun-protective behaviors. Having sunscreen and areas to seek shade conveniently available may also lead to increased sun-protective behaviors.

Personalized interventions improve adherence to sun-protective behaviors.

Darlow and Heckman (2017) examined the use of daily behavior-tracking and customized text messages on sun protection behaviors in young women at risk for skin cancer. Those that engaged in behavior-tracking had significantly fewer sun exposure behaviors (Darlow & Heckman, 2017). Darlow and Heckman (2017) concluded that interventions aimed at behavioral change could be examined with other healthy behaviors and that repetitive behavior-tracking can lead to development of healthy behaviors. Glanz et al. (2014) evaluated the impact of customized printed material on skin cancer prevention behaviors, skin self-examinations, and provider skin recommendations among adults at moderate to high risk of cancer. Participants receiving tailored risk communications had improved adherence in skin cancer protective behaviors (including sunscreen use, use of sunglasses, skin self-examinations, and frequency of skin examinations by a health care provider) compared to those given generic print communications (Glanz et al., 2014). Another study that used a culturally-sensitive sun protection workbook with text or email reminders found the intervention group had

significant increases in knowledge, perceived skin cancer risk, and willingness to change behaviors than those that did not receive the intervention (Robinson et al., 2014).

These studies suggest that patients with melasma and other conditions from sun exposure could benefit from behavior-tracking, customized text messages reminders, and customized paper communications from their HCP, prompting them to engage in sun-protective behaviors. This is in line with the HPM proposition that states interpersonal influences (HCPs) that model, expect, and support a behavior (in this case by providing tailored information about sun-protective behaviors) will increase the likelihood that the individual will commit to and engage in that behavior (Pender et al., 2011).

Technology-based interventions are useful if they are actively used. Several studies have evaluated the effectiveness of using technology to change behavior. Robinson et al. (2016) found that kidney transplant recipients who used the mobile application SunProtect (which provided educational content, interactive quizzes, and personalized sun protection messages to users regarding importance of sun protection) had significantly increased sun-protective behaviors than those that received standard education (Robinson et al., 2016). Similarly, Bowen et al. (2015) showed that melanoma survivors and their families who used a web-based intervention used had significantly improved skin self-examination and sun-protective behaviors compared with control group survivors. Smart phone applications and other technology-based interventions are useful when they are actively used. Buller et al. (2015) evaluated the use of a mobile application Solar Cell, which provided personalized sun protection advice based on skin phenotype, clothing coverage, photosensitive medications, forecasted UV index, risk of sunburn, use of sunscreen, and time until reapplication of sunscreen. Only 41% of the

treatment group used the app at least once after installment and reported using shade more than controls (Buller et al., 2015). Interestingly, treatment group users used sunscreen less than controls (Buller et al., 2015). Photodocumentation of sun damage is another intervention used to influence sun protective behaviors in those with chronic sun exposure. Although this technology can be used to show underlying damage to skin from poor sun-protection, it is only useful if individuals are willing to look at it. A study in which 257 college students were given the choice to see a personalized photograph showing sun damage and over one-third of participants opted not to see their photograph (Dwyer et al., 2015). Participants that reported infrequent sun protection behavior and that had increased perceived risk of sun damage were more likely to avoid seeing their photo UV-damaged skin (Dwyer et al., 2015).

These studies show that technology-based interventions influence behavioral change if they are actively used which highlights another important concept from the HPM. Competing demands that require immediate attention or that appear more attractive will make a commitment to a plan of action less likely to occur (Pender et al., 2011). A web-based intervention and smart phone applications regarding sun-protective behaviors could benefit melasma patients if they commit to using them; however, when competing demands are greater, commitment to using these interventions are less likely to occur.

Summary

This review of literature found that patients with melasma would benefit from interventions that focus on prevention, such as patient education regarding the importance of sun-protective behaviors and how sun-exposure exacerbates the condition. Patients with or at risk for skin cancer would benefit from interventions that: increase patient

knowledge, address perceived barriers, promote personalized support from HCPs, and utilize technology to influence behavioral change. It follows that patients with melasma would also benefit from these types of interventions, as both skin cancer and melasma exacerbations are triggered by sun-exposure. These interventions align with the propositions of the HPM, that individuals are more likely to engage in health-promoting behavior (sun-protective behaviors) when they believe the behavior will lead to a valued outcome, when perceived barriers are addressed, and when the behavior is supported by interpersonal influences (Pender et al., 2011).

METHODS

The overall goal of this mixed-methods project was to gain perspective about barriers to sun-protective behaviors in patients with melasma and to develop evidence- and data-based practice recommendations for patient education. A convergent design was utilized so that both quantitative and qualitative data was obtained in a single phase. Self-reported sun-protective behaviors was assessed through the Sun Exposure and Protection Index (SEPI) survey. Semi-structured individual interviews were conducted to better understand the lived experience of having a melasma diagnosis and participating in sun-protective behaviors.

Setting

This project was conducted at a small private practice in Orange County, California, comprised of one physician and one nurse practitioner (NP) who diagnosed and treated patients with melasma. Patients were diagnosed with melasma after a careful history and physical exam. Baseline photodocumentation was obtained through the VISIA Complexion Analysis System, a device that can detect changes in the skin consistent with numerous dermatological conditions, including melasma, and is used to track the patient's progress over time (Goldsberry et al., 2014). All patients with melasma were given verbal education regarding the importance of sun-protective behaviors. Depending on patient preference and cost, treatment options were topical prescription creams, laser and light-based modalities, and patient education on avoidance of triggers.

Recruitment

An email describing the study was sent to current patients that had provided an email address to the practice. The purpose of the email was to inform patients of the

upcoming study and that they might be asked to participate in the study when coming to the office. Purposive sampling was used to ensure information-rich sources were included in the study. Sampling continued until data saturation was met. Inclusion criteria were patients with a diagnosis of melasma, 18 years of age or older, who spoke English. Patients who met inclusion criteria were again informed of the study when they checked-in by the front desk staff. The Author/Principle Investigator (PI) checked the schedule prior to each shift to highlight patients with a diagnosis of melasma so that the front desk staff knew who to tell about the study. A flyer advertising the study was also displayed at the front desk where the patients checked-in and checked-out of the office. Patients requesting information about or expressing interest in the study were given a Study Information Sheet (Appendix C) by the front desk staff, then referred to the PI.

Ethical Conduct

Approval for this project was obtained from the physician-owner and CSUF Institutional Review Board (IRB). This section addresses ethical conduct of the study.

Informed Consent

Informed consent was obtained from patient participants (Appendix D). The informed consent form provided a detailed description of both parts of the study (survey and interviews), contact information for the PI and faculty advisors, potential risks and benefits of participation, and informed participants of their choice to participate in one or both parts of the study. At the bottom of the informed consent, participants could check a box indicating their interest in participating in a focus group or an individual interview and give consent to be audio-recorded. Informed consent was obtained by the PI prior to

completing the survey, demographics questionnaire, and/or prior to participating in the focus group/interview.

Potential for Coercion

The PI is a treatment provider for patients with melasma. To ensure patients did not feel coerced into participation, the PI did not provide the initial study information, but relied on front desk staff to ask patients if they wanted more information about the study. Study information sheets and a flyer were available in the front office area as described above. Potential participants read about the study when viewing the flyer or study information sheets in the front office area. When patients with a melasma diagnosis checked-in, the front office staff offered them an information sheet about the study. If, after reading the information sheet, the patient was interested in participating in the study, the staff member referred the patient to the PI who went over the informed consent form, components of the study (survey, demographic sheet), and answered questions about the study. The patients were told that their choice to participate or not participate would not affect their care. If patients agreed to participate in the study, the PI gained informed consent. If a patient was interested in participating in the study on a day that the PI was not in the office, the front desk staff provided the patient with the information sheet, took down the patient's name and number, and the PI called the patient. The patient was then asked to come to the office at her/his convenience.

Data Collection

Quantitative Data Collection Procedures

After consent was obtained, the patient was instructed to either complete the demographic and survey forms while in the office or mail the completed forms back to

the office. If the patient chose the latter format, the office provided a self-addressed stamped envelope. If the patient chose to complete the documents in office, the patient was instructed to place the completed forms in the packet envelope and give the envelope to the front office staff. Staff placed the envelope in a box next to their desks, but away from patients. The PI collected the packets at the end of the work day.

Qualitative Data Collection Procedures

The goal of interviewing participants was to gain understanding about the experience of having melasma and engaging in sun-protective behaviors. There were two formats for interviews offered to patients - focus groups and individual interviews - and participants indicated their preference on the informed consent form. The informed consent form also asked participants if they agreed to be audio-recorded during the focus group or individual interviews. Patients participating in focus groups or interviews were given several time options. If participants were unable to attend scheduled focus groups, they were given the option of an individual interview that was conducted at a time that was convenient for them. Due to scheduling constraints, only two participants were able to be interviewed in office and they requested individual interviews. The remaining participants requested telephonic interviews. The PI conducted all interviews.

Interviews. At the beginning of the individual interview, the PI welcomed participants, then read the focus group script and interview guide. The use of audio-recordings was detailed in the informed consent and iterated in the focus group script. If the participant agreed to be audio-recorded, the PI explained the recording process and reassured participants that no names will be included in any publication. The PI answered questions then began the interview using the interview guide. The PI asked additional

questions as needed to clarify or explore new information. When the interviews were completed, the PI thanked participants and completed field notes typed and stored on the PI's password protected computer.

Telephonic interviews. Telephonic interviews were conducted in the same process as described for individual interviews. These individuals had already completed the informed consent, demographic questionnaire, and SEPI survey while in office. Questions about the study and participation were addressed prior to proceeding with the interview. Once verbal agreement from the participant was obtained, the interview started. Data was collected via a secured online telephone service provided by the transcriptionist. Telephonic interviews were directly sent from the telephone service to the transcriptionist for transcribing.

Participants were identified on a numbered Master List, which only the PI and DNP advisors (Dr. Robertson and Dr. Parsons) had access to. The patient's assigned number was used on all interviews. Quantitative data was kept in a locked file cabinet in the PI's home. Qualitative data was stored on the PI's password protected computer and only the PI and the DNP advisors have access to the data.

Measurements

Quantitative Instruments

Two instruments were utilized for this project. a demographic questionnaire developed by the author (Appendix E) and the Sun Exposure and Protection Index [SEPI] (Appendix F). Demographic information collected was age, education level, ethnicity, self-reported Fitzpatrick skin typing, years having melasma diagnosis, how often one thinks about their melasma, and sunscreen use, including sun protection factor (SPF) and

reapplication behaviors. The SEPI has two sections. The first section contains eight questions based on five-grade Likert scale scores (0-4 points) and assesses sun-protective behaviors (for a total score of 0-32 points). A higher score reflects an increased risk of sun-exposure (Detert et al., 2015). The second section assesses readiness to increase sun-protective behaviors and consists of five questions (0-4 points) based on the TTM stages of behavioral change. A high score in the second section translates to a decreased proclivity to increase sun protection (Detert et al., 2015).

The validity and reliability of the SEPI was assessed in populations from Sweden and Australia. University students and primary health care patients were recruited to participate in the study. Participants completed the SEPI along with the Readiness to Alter Sun Protective Behaviour (RASP-B) and the Sun Protection Behaviour Scale (SPBS), both of which were based on the Transtheoretical model of behavior change (TTM) and previously validated (Detert et al., 2015). SEPI questions were compared with SPBS and showed good correlations regarding sun habits using Spearman's Rho (Detert et al., 2015). Spearman's Rho was also used to compare SEPI and RASP-B. Results were comparable for precontemplation and contemplation stages but showed slightly lower SEPI mean scores for action stage (Detert et al., 2015). To test reliability, the SEPI was filled out again one month later and test-retest analysis indicated stability over time (Detert et al., 2015). PIs concluded that the SEPI was a reliable and validated instrument.

Qualitative Interview Guide

An interview guide was developed, based on key elements of Pender's model (e.g., personal characteristics, benefits, barriers), that utilized open-ended questions to understand participants' experience of having melasma and sun-protective behaviors

(Appendix G). Follow-up questions and probes were used to explore statements and clarify meanings.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to calculate frequencies and percentages of the demographic data and SEPI survey scores (part I and II). A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to evaluate the strength of the relationship between SEPI part I and II scales. A Spearman correlation analysis was conducted to evaluate the relationship between each SEPI part I and II scales with ordinal variables. Analyses of data collected was performed using Intellectus Statistics Online Computer Software (2019) and Statistical Package for the Social Sciences [SPSS] (IBM SPSS Statistics, v.23, 2015).

Qualitative Data Analysis

Conventional content analysis as described by Hsieh and Shannon (2005) was utilized to investigate qualitative data. Data was read by the PI and DNP advisor word by word to identify key concepts, which were used to label codes. Once consensus of codes was reached, codes were sorted into categories based on meaningful relationships, then clustered into themes (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). This approach was based on inductive analysis in which data moves from specific ideas to general concepts (Carey & Asbury, 2016). After qualitative analysis was complete, both qualitative and quantitative data were integrated into an overall interpretation that was used to make recommendations for patient education.

Trustworthiness of the qualitative results was achieved in several ways. Mixed methods were used to collect varied data to build a “picture” of sun-protective behaviors.

The researchers frequently examined their opinions, preconceptions, and perceptions (reflexivity) through many discussions during the analysis (coding, categorization, developing themes). The author and project chair coded separately and compared results (credibility). Differences were discussed until a common understanding (consensus) was reached. In addition, theoretical notes were kept to illustrate the researchers' understanding of the data at the various points of analysis.

RESULTS

This section reports the results of the surveys and interviews.

Quantitative Results

Respondent Demographic Information

Twenty-one participants completed the demographic questionnaire and Sun Exposure and Protection Index (SEPI) Part 1 and II survey. Respondents ranged in age from 25 to 65 plus years. The 25-34-year age group had the highest frequency (38%) followed by the 45-54 (33%) and 35-44 (24%) age groups. The majority of respondents had a bachelor's or graduate degree (62%). They were primarily Caucasian/White (57%) or Hispanic/Latino (28%), with a small number of Asian/Pacific Islanders (14%). Sixty-two percent of participants were self-reported Fitzpatrick Skin Type IV-IV, whereas 38% self-reported as Skin Type I-III.

Eighty-four percent of participants reported having melasma for three or more years. Forty-three percent of participants thought about their melasma, "always" and 38% thought about it "often." The most frequently observed sunscreen SPF used was 30-49 (62%). Of the 21 participants, only 24% applied sunscreen every two hours as recommended; most reapplied sunscreen every 3-5 hours (28%) or 6-8 hours (10%), and 38% did not reapply sunscreen at all (Table 1).

Table 1

Demographic Data

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Age in Years		
25-34	8	38.10
35-44	5	23.81
45-54	7	33.33
65+	1	4.76
Education Level		
High school or GED	2	9.52
Some college/did not finish degree	3	14.29
Associate degree/technical degree	3	14.29
Bachelor's degree	6	28.57
Graduate degree	7	33.33
Ethnicity		
Hispanic/Latino	6	28.57
Asian/Pacific Islander	3	14.29
Caucasian/White	12	57.14
Fitzpatrick Skin Type		
I: Always burns easily, never tans	1	4.76
II: Always burns easily, tans slightly	1	4.76
III: Burns moderately, tans gradually	6	28.57
IV: Burns minimally, tans moderately	5	23.81
V: Rarely burns, tans profusely	7	33.33
VI: Never burns, tans profusely	1	4.76
Years with Melasma		
1 year	1	4.76
1-2 years	2	9.52
3-4 years	7	33.33
5-6 years	5	23.81
7 or more years	6	28.57
Thinking about Melasma		
Rarely	1	4.76
Occasionally	3	14.29
Often	8	38.10
Always	9	42.86
Sunscreen SPF		
30-49	13	61.90
50+	8	38.10

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
Sunscreen Reapplication		
do not reapply	8	38.10
every 6-8 hours	2	9.52
every 3-5 hours	6	28.57
every 2 hours	5	23.81

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

SEPI Part I

The SEPI is a two-part survey. SEPI Part I assesses sun exposure and protection habits (Table 2). When asked about sunbathing with the intention of tanning, 57% answered “never,” 38% responded “occasionally” or “seldom,” and 5% indicated they “often” sunbathed to get tanned. Sixty-two percent had no episodes of sunburn in the prior 12 months and only 24% reported three or more episodes of sunburn. The majority of participants (48%) spent less than 30 minutes in the sun between the hours of 11 am and 3pm on a typical day off and 43% spent less than two hours. Most participants reported “never” (24%) or “seldom” (48%) taking a vacation to spend time in the sun.

When asked about sun protection, 76% of participants “always” and 14% “often” used sunscreen. Sixty-six percent reported “always” or “often” using clothes to cover skin and 95% used a sun hat or cap for protection. Interestingly, 28% of participants indicated they only “occasionally” or “seldom” stayed indoors or in the shade to protect themselves from the sun.

Table 2

SEPI Part I: Sun Exposure and Protection Habits

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
SEPI I Q1: How often do you sunbathe with the intention to get tanned?		
Never	12	57.14
Seldom	5	23.81
Occasionally	3	14.29
Often	1	4.76
SEPI I Q2: How many times have you been sunburnt during the last 12 months?		
None	13	61.90
1-2 times	3	14.29
3-5 times	4	19.05
6-10 times	1	4.76
SEPI I Q3: How long do you usually stay in the sun between 11am and 3pm on a typical day off?		
< 30 min	10	47.62
30 min-1 hour	5	23.81
1-2 hours	4	19.05
2-3 hours	1	4.76
> 3 hours	1	4.76
SEPI I Q4: How often do you take a holiday with the intention of spending more time in the sun?		
Never	5	23.81
Seldom	10	47.62
1-2 weeks a year	5	23.81
3-5 weeks a year	1	4.76
SEPI I Q5: When in the sun, how often do you use sunscreen?		
Always	16	76.19
Often	3	14.29
Occasionally	1	4.76
Seldom	1	4.76
SEPI I Q6: When in the sun, how often do you use covering clothes?		
Always	7	33.33
Often	7	33.33
Occasionally	2	9.52
Seldom	4	19.05
Never	1	4.76

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
SEPI I Q7: When in the sun, how often do you use a sun hat or cap for sun protection?		
Always	11	52.38
Often	9	42.86
Seldom	1	4.76
SEPI I Q8: How often do you stay indoors or in the shade in order to protect yourself from the sun?		
Always	5	23.81
Often	10	47.62
Occasionally	3	14.29
Seldom	3	14.29

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

SEPI Part II

SEPI II assesses a participant's readiness to increase sun protection based on the TTM's stages of change (precontemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, and maintenance). A majority (72%) of participants reported having avoided sunbathing for either a long time or having given up sunbathing recently. While 19% percent were willing to think about giving up sunbathing, 5% had not considered making this change. The majority of participants had started to use sunscreen (24%) or used it for a long time (67%). The remaining participants (9%) intended to begin using sunscreens. When asked if they used clothes or head sun protection, 68% reported using clothes and 95% used a sun hat or cap. Nineteen percent (clothes) and 5% (hats) of participants would consider using these articles for sun protection. It was interesting to note that 14% had not considered using clothes for protection. Most respondents (81%) reported staying in the shade to decrease sun exposure while 9% each were willing to consider using shade or intended to begin using shade.

Table 3

SEPI Part II: Readiness to Increase Sun Protection

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
SEPI II Q1: Sunbathing		
I have never thought of giving up sunbathing	1	4.76
I could think of giving up sunbathing	4	19.05
I intend to give up sunbathing	1	4.76
I have recently given up sunbathing	2	9.52
I have for a long-time avoided sunbathing	13	61.90
SEPI II Q2: Sunscreens		
I intend to start using sunscreens	2	9.52
I have started to use sunscreens	5	23.81
I have for a long-time used sunscreens	14	66.67
SEPI II Q3: Covering clothes		
I have never thought of using covering clothes for sun protection	3	14.29
I could think of using covering clothes for sun protection	4	19.05
I have started to use covering clothes for sun protection	10	47.62
I have for a long time used covering clothes for sun protection	4	19.05
SEPI II Q4: Sun hat or cap		
I intend to start using a sun hat or cap for sun protection	1	4.76
I have started to use a sun hat or cap for sun protection	8	38.10
I have for a long time used a sun hat or cap for sun protection	12	57.14
SEPI II Q5: The shade		
I could think of trying to stay in the shade during the hours of strongest sun light	2	9.52
I intend to start trying to stay in the shade during the hours of strongest sun light	2	9.52
I have started trying to stay in the shade during the hours of strongest sun light	11	52.38
I have for a long time tried to stay in the shade during the hours of strongest sunlight	6	28.57

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Summary Statistics

A higher score on SEPI I (range = 0-32 points) indicates the participant engages in behaviors that increase risk for sun-exposure. The average total SEPI I Score was 6.81 ($SD = 4.68$, $SE_M = 1.02$, Min = 1.00, Max = 16.00). A higher score on SEPI II (range = 0-

20 total points) indicates a decreased propensity to increase sun protection (Detert et al., 2015). The average total SEPI II Score was 4.48 ($SD = 3.28$, $SE_M = 0.72$, Min = 0.00, Max = 12.00). This information is summarized in Table 4.

Table 4

SEPI I and SEPI II Mean Scores

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>SE_M</i>
SEPI I Score	6.81	4.68	21	1.02
SEPI II Score	4.48	3.28	21	0.72

Reliability

Spearman correlation analysis. A Spearman correlation analysis was conducted among Age in Years, Education Level, Fitzpatrick Skin Type, Years with Melasma, Thinking about Melasma, Sunscreen SPF, Sunscreen Reapplication, and SEPI Part I and II Scores. Cohen's (1998) standard was used to evaluate the strength of the relationships, where coefficients between .10 and .29 represent a small effect size, coefficients between .30 and .49 represent a moderate effect size, and coefficients above .50 indicate a large effect size. In a Spearman correlation, the relationship between each pair of variables cannot change direction (Conover & Iman, 1981).

A significant negative correlation was observed between Age in Years and Sunscreen Reapplication ($r_s = -0.45$, $p = .039$). The correlation coefficient suggests that as age increases, sunscreen reapplication tends to decrease. A significant positive correlation was observed between Thinking about Melasma and Sunscreen SPF ($r_s = 0.44$, $p = .044$). The correlation coefficient suggests that as time spent thinking about melasma increases, sunscreen SPF numbers tend to increase. A significant negative

correlation was observed between Sunscreen Reapplication and SEPI II Score ($r_s = -0.47$, $p = .030$). The correlation coefficient -0.47 suggests that as sunscreen reapplication increases, SEPI II Scores tend to decrease. A significant positive correlation was observed between SEPI I and SEPI II Scores ($r_s = 0.69$, $p < .001$). The correlation coefficient was 0.69 , indicating a large effect size. This correlation indicates that as SEPI I Scores increase, SEPI II Scores tend to increase. Table 5 presents the results of the correlations.

Table 5

Spearman Correlation Matrix Among Age in Years, Education Level, Fitzpatrick Skin Type, Years with Melasma, Thinking about Melasma, Sunscreen SPF, Sunscreen Reapplication, SEPI I Score, and SEPI II Score

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Age in Years	-								
2. Education Level	0.20	-							
3. Fitzpatrick Skin Type	-0.16	0.11	-						
4. Years with Melasma	0.43	0.19	-0.31	-					
5. Thinking about Melasma	0.15	0.03	0.07	0.06	-				
6. Sunscreen SPF	-0.24	-0.08	-0.15	-0.05	0.44	-			
7. Sunscreen Reapplication	-0.45	0.18	0.05	-0.15	0.10	0.40	-		
8. SEPI I Score	-0.12	-0.01	0.18	0.08	-0.27	-0.23	-0.24	-	
9. SEPI II Score	0.39	0.24	-0.21	0.32	-0.18	-0.07	-0.47	0.69	-

Note. The critical values are 0.43, 0.55, and 0.67 for significance levels .05, .01, and .001 respectively.

Qualitative Results

Thirteen participants were interviewed. Twenty-three codes were identified, then collapsed into categories and clustered into agreed upon themes. Participants spoke of Living with Melasma as a process of considering two sub-themes: Sun-Protective Behaviors and Managing Melasma, (Appendix H).

Living with Melasma

Living with melasma began when participants noted patchy hyperpigmentation on their cheeks, forehead, and around the eyes. For some participants, this pigment change began with hormone changes associated with pregnancy. For other participants, pigment changes occurred after initiating oral contraceptive medications and/or after excessive sun exposure. Some participants noted heat exacerbated the pigment. All participants understood that sun-exposure made pigment worse, but some could not relate the pathogenesis behind it: “I know it makes it darker. I don’t know how or why.”

Part of living with melasma was experiencing feelings of guilt and regret over previous sun-exposures. Most participants knew sun exposure was detrimental, “Oh, why didn’t I listen?” Others stated they were ignorant of the sun’s damaging effects, in part because when they were children, “I was in the sun for hours on end with just SPF4.”

Another participant added:

I mean I’m 46-years-old, almost 47-years-old and as kids our parents didn’t apply sunscreen to us when we were at the pool and playing outside and things like that. Then you know, I guess when I was snowboarding some people would use sunscreen, but definitely not everybody, you know. We all have the tan faces with the big goggle lines around our faces. It was cute then, but now the consequences are this . . . now are stuck with melasma from not protecting ourselves from our days of snowboarding.

Other participants reported wanting to get a tan outweighed any dangerous effects of sun exposure:

when I was younger, we would put literally baby oil on and we'd go out to the beach and it's like you're going out in the sun . . . You're going to go get a tan . . . That's like the whole purpose. You want to get a tan.

Another participant felt she was protected because of her skin tone:

I mean this is so ignorant, but I never really had to do anything . . . I'm Italian and I have olive skin and I don't burn easily. So just kind of growing up it was not really something I ever really had to worry about. So I guess I got into a bad habit of not really protecting myself unless I know I'm going to the pool or out in the sun all day long then I would, but on a daily basis I don't. It takes a lot for me to burn, get sunburned or get sun damaged.

Participants then described their current sun-protective behaviors and how they managed their melasma.

Sun-Protective Behaviors

Participants still enjoyed activities done outside during the day, such as going to the beach or pool, spending time at the park, doing yardwork and gardening, activities such as tennis, hiking, running, and walking. After becoming aware of the sun's effect of worsening melasma symptoms, most participants became "more careful" when engaging in outdoor activities and used sunscreens with higher SPF levels and hats more consistently. Some avoided outdoor activities in general, due to fear and worry of melasma getting worse: "I never feel comfortable being in the sun. I'm always so worried."

Participants protected themselves from the sun by applying sunscreen (most common), wearing hats or visors, wearing sunglasses, using umbrellas, and avoiding sun during peak hours. One participant stated:

“Even if it’s cloudy I wear a hat, a visor, glasses, but I keep my face out of the sun . . . Even if I am in the sun for a little bit I make sure that I’m covered and always have my sunscreen near.”

Nearly all participants reported using some type of sunscreen daily, although reapplication did not occur consistently. Some participants found it “difficult to reapply” over makeup or were concerned that it would “let your make-up run.” Other participants stated it was inconvenient to reapply sunscreen frequently. “Once I put it on then I’m just, I’m busy, I go on with the rest of my day and I feel like, okay, I’ve already put it on and I should be good to go.” Forgetting to reapply sunscreen was another problem, with participants stating, “If I’m hiking or doing something, I do forget” and “It’s definitely a nuisance trying to remember to reapply the sunblock.” Participants also complained that sunscreen “stings your eyes” when sweating or in water, and that sunscreens are “pretty expensive.”

Interestingly, some participants did not use or reapply sunscreens because they did not realize they were having sun exposure. One participant was only concerned about the sun while at the beach or pool saying, “I don’t know why I associate the sun being stronger at the beach than my every day . . . I go out in the sun every day.” Another participant added: “I would wear sunscreen, in the summer I wear sunscreen to the pool. I’ll put it on my face actively, but on a daily basis, outside of summer, no I don’t.” Only one participant recognized that driving is also considered sun exposure, saying: “I’m

pretty much inside a lot, but I drive all the time and I know that even if my windows are UV protected, I feel like the left side of my face has more than the right side.”

Managing Melasma

Participants managed melasma in two ways. The first was by applying topical prescription creams, receiving laser treatments, and using sun-protection, which most often included sunscreen. Make-up or concealer was used to mask or cover the hyperpigmentation, a source of increased self-consciousness and frustration for participants. Participants reported feeling “insecure” and “uncomfortable in my own skin” because melasma made them look “dirty” and “older.” One participant recalled:

I don't really consider myself a very vain person. I'm pretty natural with stuff like that and I haven't really put a lot of focus on things like that, but it's like a dark, like I said it's a dark shadow all over my face. I feel like it's making me look older. I mean I'm okay with a natural occurring wrinkles and things like that, but to me this is different. I mean it looks bad . . . It's not nice on a woman's face. It's not a nice-looking thing.

Participants were also worried that other people could see the pigment. “I feel like I always have a little bit of an insecurity where I think that people are not seeing me . . . I'm always thinking . . . are they looking at my skin?” Another participant noted, “my husband is not a superficial person, but one day he pointed at melasma and said oh it's getting worse . . . for him to notice . . . it bothered me. It made me feel bad.” One participant reported that her fear of someone seeing her skin has prevented her from dating, saying:

I mean emotionally it has affected my self-esteem because obviously when I'm so concerned and aware of my skin pigmentation problem I don't really want to date or do anything like that because I don't want anybody to really see how bad my skin looks without makeup . . . I have been now single for 18 years.

Another participant reported that insecurity from Melasma is interfering with her professional career. She reported:

I've been asked by my design team and people that are helping me for almost a year now to put my face on the site, put my face on the Instagram account, start telling stories, start getting live, start getting active . . . So I haven't done that . . . I mean I barely have put together a LinkedIn headshot only because a girlfriend of mine is a famous photographer, so she's really good at Photoshop . . . I've definitely shied away from those things because of the melasma.

Another issue associated with feelings of insecurity was the actual time and effort it took to apply makeup. Having to constantly apply makeup was described as "annoying", "time-consuming", and "inconvenient." One participant said:

It's awful. I cannot leave the house without wearing makeup because there's such a disparaging color differentiation between the light and the dark on my skin and it's just so obvious. So I'm not comfortable leaving the house without makeup to kind of blend in the two colors . . . you know it just takes far more finesse and time for application to kind of finesse it and not make it so obvious that I'm wearing several shades darker than I should be.

Regarding time, another participant questioned, “If you added it up I’m sure it would be hours upon hours that I’m having to stop, put makeup on, instead of going out and enjoying my life . . . how much of my life did I really miss?”

The second way they managed melasma was seeking treatment options that were effective and affordable. Participants desired options that were more curative, stating they wanted to know “how to fix it” and desired a “more permanent solution.” One participant was frustrated over the lack of progress in finding an effective treatment saying,

I think it’s honestly more of that nobody knows what to do about it. So there’s like no plan around it . . . Why are we having such a difficulty in how to block these melanin developments? It’s been just perplexing to me. We’re sending Teslas to Mars, but this is something that nobody has any idea.

Participants stated that treatment options were expensive, especially when they “aren’t 100% sure that they’re going to work.” Another participant added, “Those treatments, as you know, can be anywhere from a couple hundred dollars a treatment all the way to thousands of dollars a treatment . . . People that are desperate will pay anything and the market knows that as well.” Aside from in-office treatment costs, participants were concerned about the cost associated with sunscreens, prescription creams, and makeup, and frustrated over a lack of insurance coverage for their condition. “It’s still looked at as cosmetic when I don’t feel in my personal opinion that it’s cosmetic in any way, shape or form. I feel like it’s an actual disease, but the medical industry doesn’t treat it as that.”

Summary

SEPI survey results indicated increased engagement and readiness to engage in sun-protective behaviors for most participants. Despite this, only 24% of participants reapplied sunscreen every two hours as recommended. Barriers to sun-protective behaviors revealed through participant interviews were being ignorant to the sun's damaging effect on melasma, not recognizing incidental sun exposure risk, and not using sunscreen appropriately.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this project was to gain perspective about barriers to sun-protective behaviors of patients with melasma and to develop evidence- and data-based practice recommendations for patient education. Guided by the Health Promotion Model (HPM) and Transtheoretical Model (TTM), this project identified potential barriers to sun-protective behaviors and assessed the participant's readiness to increase sun-protective behaviors. Self-reported sun-protective behaviors were assessed through Part I of the Sun Exposure and Protection Index (SEPI) Survey. The SEPI Part II section assessed the participants readiness to change or increase sun-protective behaviors based on the TTM's stages of change (precontemplation, contemplation, preparation, action, and maintenance). Understanding the experience of having melasma and practicing sun-protective behaviors was revealed through semi-structured interviews. The theme and sub-themes that emerged in from the interviews identified additional behaviors and barriers to sun-protection.

Sun-Protective Behaviors in Patients with Melasma

Patients with melasma are generally motivated to have healthier skin and improve their appearance. The majority of participants had low scores on SEPI Part I (indicating that they engaged in sun-protective behaviors), which correlated with the lower scores on SEPI Part II (indicating increased readiness to engage in sun-protective behaviors). Statistical analysis indicated that as SEPI I scores increased, SEPI II scores also increased. This is consistent with findings by Detert et al. (2015) which showed that higher scores in both sections of the SEPI tool indicated increased risk for sun exposure and a higher proclivity to decrease sun-protective behaviors (Detert et al., 2015). In

addition, results showed that SEPI II scores tended to decrease as sunscreen reapplication increased, representing consistent engagement in a variety of sun-protective behaviors, including sunscreen use. Data analysis revealed that as time thinking about melasma increased, sunscreen SPF numbers tended to increase. Participant interviews confirmed this by stating having melasma made them more educated and aware that they needed to avoid the sun and wear sunscreen with higher SPF ratings. In addition, because their melasma was on their face, it was a constant presence and reminder to avoid sun. This is consistent with Maymone et al.'s (2017) findings that patients with melasma are more motivated to use sunscreen compared with patients with other hyperpigmentation disorders.

Barriers to Sun-Protective Behaviors in Patients with Melasma

Barriers to sun-protective behaviors revealed through participant interviews were: a lack of knowledge, a lack of perceived risk, and inconsistent use of sunscreen.

Lack of Knowledge

Participants reported that their parents did not place importance on sun-protection in their youth, and they were ignorant to the sun's damaging effects on melasma. Most knowledge regarding sun protective behaviors are from parents and family members (Bruce et al., 2017). Participants also reported that they wished they knew to avoid the sun sooner. Because most of the damage occurred in their younger years, and because melasma can be triggered by hormone fluctuations, it may benefit young patients to be educated about sun protection before the onset of menses. This is aligned with the United States Preventive Services Task Force (2018) recommendations to educate young adults, adolescents, children, and parents of young children about minimizing sun exposure for

persons aged 6 months to 24 years (US Preventive Services Task Force, 2018).

Additionally, it is well-known that increasing knowledge contributes to increased engagement in sun-protective behaviors (Smith et al., 2018; Maymone et al., 2017; Kamimura et al, 2015; Bagatti et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2014; Hernandez et al., 2014).

Lack of Perceived Risk

Participants reported having much more sun exposure than they realized. They practiced sun-protective behaviors more consistently in the summer or when near the pool or at the beach, not recognizing that sun exposure occurred anytime that they were outside, next to an open window, or when driving. A lack of perceived risk while engaging in outdoor activities and when driving appears to occur in other adult populations and suggests more patient education is needed regarding incidental sun exposure risks (Bruce et al., 2017; Holman et al., 2014; Kim et al., 2013). Incidental sun exposure can occur anytime a patient is outside during the day, including activities as short as walking from the front door to the mailbox, to longer activities like walking around an outdoor mall. Key organizations and stakeholders can address incidental sun exposure by creating recreational environments that have shaded areas, encouraging sunscreen use with reapplication prompts where people will see it, and promoting clothing with adequate SPF protection (Holman et al., 2014).

Statistical analysis indicated that as age increased, sunscreen reapplication decreased. The idea that increased age led to less sunscreen use was not supported in the interviews, rather participants reported they engaged in more sunscreen use as they were older, as this was after they received more patient education regarding the harmful effects of the sun. Re-examination of the demographic data revealed that participants that did not

reapply sunscreen as often were mainly Hispanic/Latino and Asian/Pacific Islander ethnicities. In the interview portion at least one participant believed her darker skin tone would protect her from the harmful effects of the sun. The lower perceived risk of sun damage in participants with darker skin has been examined in other studies indicating more education may be needed regarding sun exposure risk in patient with darker skin tones (Maymone et al., 2017; Jacobsen et al., 2016; Hernandez et al., 2014). Educational materials tailored to the patient's age and ethnicity have increased sun-protective behaviors in other studies (Glanz et al., 2014).

Inconsistent Sunscreen Use

Although patients with melasma may be more motivated to engage in sun-protective behaviors compared to patients without hyperpigmentation issues, reapplication of sunscreen has remained a challenge for those with and without the disease (Maymone et. al, 2017; Holman et al., 2014). Most participants completed SEPI Part I with answers that indicated increased sun-protective behaviors. For example, the majority of participants answered that they “always” wear sunscreen, but when combined with the demographic questionnaire results, it is revealed that although all participants wore sunscreen, 77% did not reapply sunscreen at recommended intervals, leaving their skin unprotected for extended periods of time. This is similar to other studies that investigated reapplication of sunscreen and suggests that more patient education is needed to inform patients about how to choose and reapply sunscreen appropriately (Chao et al., 2017; Maymone et al., 2017).

Barriers to sunscreen reapplication included: forgetting to reapply, feeling it was inconvenient to reapply, feeling it was too expensive to reapply, and not wanting the

sunscreen to “sting” the eyes, but the most frequently answered reason for why participants did not reapply sunscreen was because they did not want to reapply it over their makeup. In other studies, barriers of sunscreen compliance were related to cost, forgetfulness, and not liking the esthetic features of the sunscreens such as greasiness, messy application, sticky after-feel, and stinging of the eyes (Wang et al., 2017). Texture issues with creams stemmed from the active ingredients and UV filters in the sunscreens. Organic sunscreens tend to be oily and viscous, whereas water-resistant sunscreens (that form a physical film over the skin) tend to feel tacky and greasy, making them unpleasant to use (Wang et al., 2017). Sprays can be more convenient to use because they generally provide a non-greasy feel and dry quickly due to the present of ethanol; however, the ethanol can cause skin irritation and be a flammability hazard (Osterwalder et al., 2014). Many foundation products now have UV protection added with the aim of covering skin imperfections while also offering sun protection (Osterwalder et al., 2014). The issue of reapplication remains a challenge, as the protective effect of the sunscreen wears off in two hours. Newer products, like powdered sunscreens still have to be reapplied every two hours but appear to be more convenient and easier to apply over makeup which may lead to increased utilization in patients with melasma.

Using the Health Promotion Model and Transtheoretical Model to Promote Sun-Protective Behaviors

This study and others show how a lack of knowledge, a lack of perceived risk, and perceived barriers lead to decreased and/or inconsistent sun-protective behaviors (Jacobsen et al., 2016; Hernandez et al., 2014; Fischer et al., 2016; Kim et al. 2013; Hobbs et al., 2014; Nahar et al., 2014; Auerbach et al., 2018; Hay et al. 2017). Using the HPM as a guide, health care providers (HCPs), a key source of interpersonal influence for

the patient, can educate and motivate the patient to engage in sun-protective behaviors more consistently. Studies have shown that increased knowledge increases engagement in sun-protective behaviors (Smith et al., 2018; Maymone et al., 2017; Kamimura et al., 2015; Bagatti et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2014; Hernandez et al., 2014). In addition, HCPs and other significant others that support sun-protective behaviors directly impact the individual's commitment to and engagement in sun-protective behaviors (Pender et al., 2011; Yockey et al., 2017; Boyas & Nahar, 2018; Mihalis et al., 2013). Using the TTM, HCPs can determine the patient's TTM stage and design interventions that can motivate the individual to transition from one stage to another, or to maintain a current stage. It is well-known that personalized interventions improve adherence to sun-protective behaviors (Darlow & Heckman, 2017; Glanz et al., 2014; Robinson et al., 2014) and the TTM has been successful in other studies investigating sun-protective behaviors (Santiago-Rivas et al., 2013; Santiago-Rivas et al., 2015; Yin et al., 2014; Babbitt et al., 2015; Brick et al., 2016; Yusufov et al., 2016; Sillice et al., 2018).

Implications for Practice

The goal of this project was to gain understanding about barriers to sun-protective behaviors of patients with melasma and to develop evidence-and data-based practice recommendations for patient education. Although patients with melasma are instructed to engage in sun-protective behaviors, such as avoiding the sun, seeking shade, and wearing protective clothing and sunscreen consistently, this study revealed that there was still a lack of knowledge of and perceived risk regarding incidental sun exposure and proper sunscreen use. Providers must do a better job of assessing the patient's understanding of sun exposure and melasma exacerbations, incidental sun exposure risk, and proper

application and reapplication of sunscreen. Assessing the patient's understanding of sun exposure risk is especially important in patients with darker skin phenotypes, as these patients may believe that their darker skin is protective against the sun's damaging effects.

Assessment of understanding and education regarding sun protection must be ongoing. Educational materials should provide examples of incidental sun exposures, such as sun exposure while driving. Sunscreen education materials should detail how to correctly apply sunscreen and emphasize the frequency of reapplication. Patients should also be educated about the various types of sunscreens (lotions, sprays, powders) and encouraged to use the type that would be most convenient for the individual to use consistently. Even when patients are aware of correct sunscreen usage and know the risks of incidental sun exposures, ultimately engaging in consistent sun-protection requires the patient to adhere to behavioral changes. Providers can utilize the HPM to directly impact the patient's commitment to and engagement in sun-protective behaviors. The TTM can be used to determine the patient's TTM stage and design interventions to motivate the individual to transition from one stage to another, or to maintain a current stage.

Aside from assessing and educating the patient regarding sun-protective behaviors, the provider must also inquire about the patient's experience of living with melasma. Participants in this study discussed a variety of feelings: guilt and frustration from past sun exposures, insecurity and self-consciousness about their physical appearance, and anger and frustration regarding a lack of effective and affordable treatment options. Providers should inquire about and acknowledge the patient's feelings about living melasma and create an individualized treatment plan to significantly

decrease the hyperpigmentation while improving the patient's feelings about their appearance. The treatment plan should include a variety of options that are cost-effective and acceptable to the patient. Providers should also advocate on the patient's behalf for melasma treatments to be more affordable and covered by insurance.

Implications for Future Research

This mixed-methods study uncovered important insights into sun-protective behaviors of patients living with melasma and should be investigated further. Because melasma disproportionately affects women with darker skin phenotypes, it would be important for future research to include a more diverse population sample. Melasma also occurs in male populations and it would be important to investigate how male patients protect themselves from the sun compared to their female counterparts. Additional studies should also evaluate how patients choose and reapply sunscreens, and how patients perceive their sun exposure risk. Although the purpose of this study was to investigate sun-protective behaviors in patients with melasma, other sub-themes were revealed such as: increased self-consciousness, feeling the need to cover-up the skin, and being frustrated with ineffective and costly treatments. Similar themes were discovered in other studies that investigated quality of life in melasma patients (Jiang et al., 2018; Ikino et al., 2015; Handel et al., 2014; Sheth & Pandya, 2011a). These themes deserve to be investigated in more detail.

Limitations

This study was limited by its small sample size of all female and mainly Caucasian, young adult participants which may be difficult to generalize to other populations. The sample was restricted to patients in Orange County, California which

may not be representative of other patients in different geographical locations. Statistically significant results are limited by the small sample size. Potential bias may have occurred due to the open-ended nature of the interview questions, although the author tried to avoid leading questions and remain neutral throughout the interview process. Reporter bias may have occurred if participants tried to answer questions in a way that would please the author, who is also their treatment provider.

Conclusion

Sun exposure is the greatest triggering factor in melasma, yet few studies investigate how patients with melasma practice sun-protective behaviors such as avoiding sun exposure, seeking shade, choosing appropriate sunscreen, and using sunscreen correctly. It is imperative for patients with melasma to practice sun-protective behaviors to delay or prevent melasma exacerbations and now barriers to sun-protective behaviors have been identified. Barriers to sun-protective behaviors in patients with melasma include a lack of knowledge, a lack of perceived risk, and a lack of consistent sunscreen use. Patients with melasma would benefit from ongoing interventions that: increase patient knowledge, address perceived barriers, and promote personalized support from HCPs. In addition to providing general sun-protective information, interventions should also focus on how to choose, apply, and reapply sunscreens, and how to recognize incidental sun exposure and minimize risk.

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APPENDIX A
LITERATURE SEARCH STRATEGY

Table A1

Sun-Protective Behaviors

Database	Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Academic Search Complete	Sun-protective behaviors	Peer reviewed, English	20	20	0	0
CINAHL	OR	language, Studies	2	0	2	2
Google Scholar	sunscreen	published in the U.S., Adult	18	10	8	1
ScienceDirect	AND melasma	population, Publish date: 2013 - 2018	1	0	1	1
PsychINFO			0	0	0	0
PubMed			41	36	5	0
Academic Search Complete	Sun-protective behaviors	Peer reviewed, English	2	1	1	1
CINAHL	AND skin cancer	language, Published in the U.S., Adult	6	1	5	5
Google Scholar		population, Publish date: 2013 - 2018	21	15	6	4
ScienceDirect			32	22	10	5
PsychINFO			7	6	1	1
PubMed			48	16	32	14

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic. Duplicates were also omitted.

Table A2

Survey Tools and Questionnaires

Database	Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Academic Search Complete	Survey or questionnaire	Peer reviewed, English	3	3	0	0
CINAHL	AND melasma	English	6	6	0	0
Google Scholar	("validated questionnaire"	Published in the U.S.,	9	3	6	2
ScienceDirect	AND melasma	Adult	1	0	1	0
PsychINFO	for google scholar)	population,	0	0	0	0
PubMed		Publish date: 2013 - 2018	21	21	0	0
Academic Search Complete	Survey or questionnaire	Peer reviewed, English	4	0	4	3
CINAHL	AND sun-protective	language, Published in the U.S.,	15	5	10	6
Google Scholar	behaviors ("validated questionnaire"	Adult	25	22	3	1
ScienceDirect	AND sun-protective	population,	1	0	1	0
PsychINFO	AND sun-protective	Publish date: 2013 - 2018	26	14	12	4
PubMed	behaviors for google scholar; "questionnaire" AND sun-protective behaviors for PubMed)		14	7	7	1
Academic Search Complete	Reliability and validity AND MASI OR mMASI	Peer reviewed, English	4	4	0	0
CINAHL		language, Published in the U.S.,	2	2	0	0
Google Scholar		Adult	15	14	1	0
ScienceDirect		population,	2	1	1	0
PsychINFO		Publish date: 2013 - 2018	0	0	0	0
PubMed			0	0	0	0
Academic Search Complete	Reliability and validity AND MELAQoL	Peer reviewed, English	2	2	0	0
CINAHL		language, Published in the U.S.,	0	0	0	0
Google Scholar		Adult	17	16	1	1
ScienceDirect		population,	0	0	0	0
PsychINFO		Publish date: 2013 - 2018	0	0	0	0
PubMed			0	0	0	0

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic. Duplicates were also omitted.

Table A3

Frameworks

Database	Terms	Limiters	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Academic Search Complete	“Health promotion model” and melasma	Peer reviewed, English language, Published in the U.S., Adult population, Publish date: 2013 - 2018	0	0	0	0
Academic Search Complete	“Health promotion model” and sun-protective behaviors	Peer reviewed, English language, Published in the U.S., Adult population, Publish date: 2013 - 2018	0	0	0	0
Academic Search Complete	“Transtheoretical model” and melasma	Peer reviewed, English language, Published in the U.S., Adult population, Publish date: 2013 - 2018	0	0	0	0
Academic Search Complete	“Transtheoretical model” and sun-protective behaviors	Peer reviewed, English language, Published in the U.S., Adult population, Publish date: 2013 - 2018	6	1	5	2

Note. Articles excluded were based on title and relevance to project topic. Duplicates were also omitted.

APPENDIX B
TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table B1

Sun-Protective Behaviors in Patients with Melasma

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To examine sun-protective behaviors and their association with demographic and clinical factors in patients with cutaneous hyperpigmentation disorders (Melasma, PIH, other disorders of hyper-pigmentation) (Maymone et al., 2017)	<p>Non-experimental; Descriptive cross-sectional study</p> <p>Key Variables: sunscreen use, SPF strength, broad spectrum use, frequency of application, amount of time in sun, wearing a hat, seeking shade, and duration of hyper-pigmentation</p> <p>Key Demographics: ages 18-55+, sex, race (white, African American, Hispanic or Latino, Asian, Native American), education level, skin</p>	<p>Participants included 404 adults with hyper-pigmentation of the skin that sought care at the Boston Medical Center or East Boston Neighborhood Health Center from 2/2015-7/2016</p> <p>424 were invited to participate, 404 completed the survey (response rate of 95%)</p> <p>89.1% were women, 47.5% were Hispanic or Latino, 56.9% were 25-44 years of age</p>	<p>Data collection included 2 parts: anonymous paper survey in English, Spanish, or Portuguese and a clinical evaluation by a trained dermatologist in which a diagnosis and skin-typing was made (based on clinical presentation and history)</p> <p>Survey included questions related to demographics, sunscreen use, SPF use, and sun protective measures (wearing hats, seeking shade)</p>	<p>Overall findings: 67.5% reported using sunscreen- of those, 91% used SPF 21 or higher, 69.3% reapplied 1-3 times daily, 48.5% were unsure if sunscreen had broad-spectrum protection, 7.6% reapplied every 2 hours. Females were more likely to use sunscreen (OR=3.8, p=.0004) and those with disease duration of ≥ 1 year were more likely to use sunscreen (OR=2.1, p=.003). The odds ratio of sunscreen use among African Americans compared to whites was 0.31 (p = .008).</p> <p>Related to Melasma:</p>	<p>Conclusions: Even for motivated patients (those with hyperpigmentation disorders), sun protective education is needed. Education should focus on the importance of reapplying sunscreen every 2 hours, rather than just using sunscreen in general.</p> <p>Limitations: possible recall bias, reporter bias, and question misinterpretation; sample mainly female and therefore not generalizable to males.</p> <p>Useful for project: Patients with melasma would benefit from</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
	typing (I-VI), and diagnosis (Melasma, PIH, other)			<p>161 (40.45%) participants were diagnosed with Melasma. Melasma patients were more likely to attribute their condition to the sun (55.1%) compared with PIH (12.1%) and other disorders (32.7%) (p=.001). Odds of a melasma patient using sunscreen was 6.7 times the odds of a PIH patient using sunscreen (p=.001). Melasma patients were more likely to seek shade (52.4%) compared with PIH (21.7%) and other conditions (25.8%) (p=.001).</p>	<p>additional sun protection education. Some may not be aware of the importance of reapplying sunscreen every 2 hours.</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To evaluate the protective properties against melasma relapses of sunscreen protecting against UVA/UVB and the shorter wavelengths of visible light compared to sunscreen with UVA/UVB protection, but without shorter wavelength protection (Boukari et al., 2015).	<p>Randomized controlled trial during the spring and summer</p> <p>Key variables: MASI scores, Formula 1 (UV and visible light protection-tinted) and Formula 2 sunscreen (UV protection only).</p> <p>Comparison between MASI scores before prevention treatment and after 6 months</p> <p>MASI scores are evaluated by two physicians blinded to the treatment received on standardized pictures taken before treatment and after 6 months of summer period</p>	<p>40 women 18 years and older with melasma randomized into 2 groups: one group using sunscreen with UV and visible light protection, the other group using sunscreen with UV protection only.</p> <p>Recruited through clinicaltrials.gov</p> <p>Formula 1 group: mean age 43 years with melasma duration of 7.9 years</p> <p>Formula 2 group: mean age 41.4 years with melasma duration of 9.7 years</p>	<p>Participants were trained on the correct dosage to be applied (1 tsp applied to face)</p> <p>Participants instructed to apply sunscreen twice daily (morning and afternoon) and to apply every 2 hours when planning on sun exposure (30 minutes before exposure)</p> <p>Main evaluation criterion: the MASI score assessed from standardized photographs (system VISIA, Canfield Scientific, USA) at Baseline, middle and end of study.</p>	<p>Increase in MASI score from baseline to 6 months greater in Formula B group (2.43 interquartile range; 0.45 to 3.68) than with Formula A (0.45 interquartile range; 0.0 to 1.65) (P = .027).</p>	<p>Conclusions: Tinted sunscreen offered partial protection in the targeted visible wavelengths. Better protection against those wavelengths may result in fewer melasma exacerbations</p> <p>Limitations: Caucasian patients-may not be generalizable to other populations. Cannot guarantee that patients used the same dose or applied product as directed. Does not account for other factors that contribute to melasma exacerbations (heat, inflammation, and hormones)</p> <p>For Project: Recommendations regarding sunscreen choice should include products that protect against visible light wavelengths</p>

PIH = Postinflammatory Hyperpigmentation, MASI = Melasma Area and Severity Index, Sun Protection Factor, UVA = Ultraviolet A, UVB = Ultraviolet B

Table B2

Sun Protective Behaviors in Patients with Skin Cancer or at High Risk for Skin Cancer

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To understand the low rates of sun protection in young women at risk for skin cancer (Auerbach et al., 2018).	Utilizing data from a previous RCT pilot study that examined effects of daily behavior tracking and individually tailored sun-safe behaviors in young women Key Variables: Behavior-tracking interventions and individually tailored text messages. Behavior tracking included daily entries asking about sun exposure. Text messages designed on Health Belief Model (HBM) constructs.	661 daily diary entries received via text message over 14 days from 56 young women at risk for skin cancer. Original study: Convenience sample recruited through online postings, email announcements at local universities, train stations, and community bulletin boards. Inclusion criteria: adult females (18-29 years) with a moderate to high risk of skin cancer based on assessment tool and must own a mobile phone. Exclusion criteria: history of skin cancer	Brief Skin Cancer Risk Assessment Tool used at baseline Daily diary measures: asking about protection, reasons for protection and reasons for non-protection HBM constructs: Perceived skin damage, perceived severity of and worry about skin cancer. Perceived benefits of using sun protection. Perceived barriers of using sun protection.	48.3% of women reported using protection. On average, participants reported using sunscreen about ½ the time. 12.5% used protection for all 14 days, 8.9% did not use any type of protection. Reasons for protection included: habit, prevent burning, prevent skin damage, prevent aging. Reasons for not protecting included: not-needed or unprepared	Conclusion: Women with higher overall sun protection were more likely to perceive greater benefits of using sun protection. Habit and prevention of sunscreen were most important reasons for protection. Forgetfulness (unprepared) was common barrier to using protection and not-needed was another (when cloudy or weather was cool) Limitations: Small sample of only women may not translate to other populations. Useful for project: Melasma patients would benefit from education regarding risk with cool weather/cloudy. Also benefit from habitual use of protection.

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To assess level of education and personal practices or medical students regarding skin examinations and sun protective behaviors (Smith et al., 2018).	<p>Non-experimental; descriptive survey</p> <p>Key Variables: Demographics: Age, sex, educational level Knowledge: skin cancer risk, knowledge and use of sun-protective behaviors, barriers to protective behaviors</p>	<p>University of Kansas School of Medicine, University of Missouri-Kansas City School of Medicine, and Kansas City University of Medicine and Biosciences medical schools</p> <p>Convenience sampling through school email accounts in fall semester of 2012 to all med students from 3 schools.</p> <p>471 student participants</p>	22-question survey developed after review of literature assessing skin characteristics and personal sun practices.	92.6% used one or more forms of sun protection. 60.7% had been educated regarding risk factors for preventing skin cancer. Participants that had been educated on how to perform a complete skin exam were significantly more likely to have used sun protective equipment in the last year and believed their medical education changed their belief about tanned skin.	<p>Conclusion: Medical school students have better sun protective practices because they are educated about skin cancer and potential risk factors. Increasing education in the public would increase engagement in sun-protective behaviors.</p> <p>Limitations: Only assesses knowledge in medical students and may not be generalizable to general population.</p> <p>Useful for project: Increasing patient's knowledge of melasma and complications may increase likelihood that the patient will engage in sun-protective behaviors</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To examine daily behavior tracking and individually tailored text messages on sun protection and UVR exposure behaviors in young women at risk for skin cancer (Darlow & Heckman, 2017).	<p>Experimental: randomized controlled design</p> <p>Key Variables: Behavior-tracking interventions and individually tailored text messages based on focus group (females ages 18-25) feedback regarding interventions. Behavior tracking included daily entries asking about sun exposure. Text messages designed on HBM constructs.</p>	<p>Metropolitan region of northeast U.S. Convenience sample recruited through online postings, email announcements at local universities, local flyers at colleges and universities, train stations, and community bulletin boards.</p> <p>Inclusion criteria: adult females (18-29 years) with a moderate to high risk of skin cancer based on assessment tool and must own a mobile phone.</p> <p>Exclusion criteria: history of skin cancer</p> <p>88.5% White, 6.7% Asian American or Pacific Islander, 1.9% Black, and 2.9% other or mixed. About 4% were Hispanic/Latino</p> <p>Large, urban cancer center</p>	<p>104 adult women at risk for skin cancer randomized in to 4 groups. Group 1 received behavior-tracking intervention only, group 2 received text messages only, group 3 had both, group 4 had neither.</p> <p>Outcomes were self-reported UVR exposure and sun-protective behaviors</p> <p>UVR exposure behaviors (wearing clothes that expose skin, using tanning devices, sunbathing, and using products to receive a deeper tan). Sun-protective behaviors included wearing sunscreen (with spf 15 or more), wearing a hat, staying in shade.</p>	<p>At 4-week follow-up: Those in behavior-tracking group had significantly fewer UVR exposure behaviors. Those who received daily tailored text messages had significantly greater UVR exposure but were more likely to wear a hat compared with those who did not receive texts.</p>	<p>Conclusions: Interventions aimed at behavioral change should be examined with other healthy behaviors.</p> <p>Limitations: Small sample size. Sample mainly white participants from one region of the U.S. with access to mobile phones. May not represent other populations.</p> <p>Useful for project: Behavior-tracking and text messages may be useful ways to remind melasma patients to practice sun-protective behaviors.</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To describe consistency of sun protection practices (sunscreen use, shade-seeking, hat use, protective clothing use) over time in melanoma 1 st degree relatives and to examine importance of decision factors in sun protection strategies (Hay et al., 2017).	Mixed-methods study design Key variables: sun protection usages (sunscreen, shade, hats, protective clothing) and decisional factors (weather, type of activity, convenience, and social support).	Convenience sample of melanoma patients approached in surgical follow-up clinics and asked to refer any potential 1 st degree relative. Inclusion criteria: must be 18 years of age or older, English speaking, and report at least 1 hr of outdoor activities every morning and afternoon 59 participants in study. Interactive voice response system on cell phone used twice daily to assess real-time sun protection usage and decisional factors	An interactive voice response system (IVRS) called participants twice daily to assess morning and afternoon sun protection across a 14-day period from May to October. They also completed audio narrative to provide qualitative feedback.	61% of participants used sunscreen inconsistently. Sunscreen and hats were used together about 40% of the time. Sunscreen use was related to the perception of having adequate time to apply it whereas shade and hat usage were related to convenience. Sunscreen use was less likely to occur when it was cloudy outside. Seeking shade occurred when it was hot outside.	Conclusion: Sun protection use has been inconsistent and understanding factors that drive sun protection choices could lead to developments that promote sun protection. Limitations: Mainly female participants with average age of 48 years. May not be generalizable to other populations. Also limited by sample had to engage in sun exposure every day Useful for project: Would be informative to ask melasma patients about their sun-protective behaviors in real time to be able to tailor interventions to their specific preferences

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To compare the sunburn protection effects of a beach umbrella vs a high-SPF sunscreen side by side in a beach setting (Ou-Yang, et al., 2017).	<p>Single-center, evaluator-blinded, randomized clinical study</p> <p>Key variables: Commercially available beach umbrella 203 cm diameter and 190 cm high. Transmission of UV rays through umbrella measured with spectrophotometer</p> <p>Preweighted sunscreen SPF of 100, tested to be water resistant for 80 minutes and photostable</p>	<p>81 participants randomly assigned to sunscreen (n=40) or umbrella group (n=41).</p> <p>Study conducted from 8-13 to 8-15 2014 at Lake Lewisville, Texas</p> <p>Inclusion criteria: no evidence of sunburn Exclusion criteria: participants with phototoxic and photoallergic reactions</p>	<p>At baseline, 7 exposed skin areas clinically examined (face, upper back, back of neck, arms, and legs). Participants instructed to stay at beach between 10 am and 2 pm and could not engage in water activities.</p> <p>Umbrella group told to stay under umbrella without wearing clothes that would block evaluated areas.</p> <p>Sunscreen group told to apply product liberally to all exposed areas of skin 15 minutes before beach exposure and reapply at least every 2 hrs or as needed (after sweating)</p>	<p>22-24 hours after sun exposure: Both groups had a significant increase in global sunburn scores from baseline</p> <p>Total number of sunburn areas was 142 for umbrella group and 17 for sunscreen group</p> <p>Umbrella group had significant increase in sunburn scores from baseline for all body sites examined vs sunscreen group</p> <p>78% of umbrella group showed erythema in 1 or more sites vs 25% of sunscreen group</p> <p>Neither umbrella or sunscreen alone completely prevented sunburn</p>	<p>Conclusion: Multiple sun protection measures (shade, avoid sun, using sunscreen, wearing hats and clothing) are necessary to provide optimal protection for extended UV exposure</p> <p>Limitations: only one type of umbrella and one type of sunscreen studied.</p> <p>Useful for project: This shows that sunscreen alone is not sufficient for melasma (or any) patients and that sun-protective behaviors as a whole must be used.</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To determine effect of educational intervention on knowledge, behavior, and attitudes of female college athletes regarding melanoma (Bagatti, Englert, & Cline, 2016).	<p>Quasi-experimental 1 group pre-test/post-test design</p> <p>Key variables: Knowledge, behavior, and attitude regarding melanoma</p>	<p>Small, private, liberal arts university in Western Pennsylvania fall semester of 2014</p> <p>Conducted at where practices were held (rowing, soccer, lacrosse)</p> <p>Convenience sample of 72 female college athletes (90.3% white, 2.8% black, 2.8% Latino, 1.4% Asian, 1.4% Pacific Islander). Subjects between ages 18-22 with mean age of 19.74 years</p>	<p>Pre-test: 28-item melanoma questionnaire assessing risk, knowledge, and sun-protective behavior (validated in Scotland and Australia, but not U.S.)</p> <p>4 colored images of normal and abnormal nevi from The Skin Cancer Foundation also used to assess ability of subject to identify suspicious lesions</p> <p>Educational intervention immediately followed questionnaire and 4 images consisting of And post-test after included 4 questions from the 28-item survey and 12 “other” questions with 4 additional colored nevi photos</p>	<p>50% reported spending 10-15 hours in sun per week (with soccer players spending the most time). Range of time in sun from 2-28 hours with average of 15.03 hours per week.</p> <p>52.8% reported prior use of a tanning device 80.6% reported sunburn at least 3 times in their lifetime 86.1% reported they attempt to suntan when on vacation Only 23.6% report using sunscreen. 76.4% report not using sunscreen. 79.2% reported intent to use sunscreen after intervention</p> <p>Other data about knowledge and identification of moles and intent to seek care</p>	<p>Conclusions: College athletes spend considerable time in sun and are at risk for melanoma. Sunburns and use of tanning devices are high. Administrators and coaches are source of information regarding sun-protective behaviors. Brief interventions increase sun-protective behaviors.</p> <p>Limitations: Convenience sample of mainly white participants in one university may not be generalizable to other populations. Related to project: Educational interventions increase sun-protective behaviors. Significant others (HPM) can increase sun-protective behaviors.</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To examine whether those with previous nonmelanoma skin cancer (NMSC) engage in better sun-protection than those without history of skin cancer (Fischer, Wang, Kang, & Chein, 2016).	Retrospective analysis of the National Health Interview Survey (NHIS) Key variables: Survey includes basic health and demographic questions. This report includes specific information related to sun protective behaviors	Self-reported data from 2005 and 2010 NHIS. Inclusion criteria was non-Hispanic white adults with (758) and without previous NMSC (34,161).	A self-administered survey was completed. Participants were asked about seeking shade, use of sun-protective clothing (wide-brimmed hats, long-sleeved shirts, clothes to ankles), using sunscreen when outdoors, SPF of sunscreen	Participants with previous NMSC compared with those with no history of NMSC had higher rates of use of shade (44.3% vs 27%), long sleeves (20.5% vs 7.7%), wide-brimmed hats (26.1% vs 10.5%), and sunscreen (53.7% vs 33.1%). Those with previous NMSC did not have lower sunburn odds. 66.9% of individuals aged 18 to 39 years with previous NMSC reported recent sunburn Among those with previous NMSC, recent sunburn was inversely related to age, sun avoidance, and shade but not sunscreen.	Conclusion: Educational counseling must also emphasize shade and sun avoidance in addition to sunscreen- especially in younger adults. Limitations: Study limited to non-Hispanic white adults and not generalizable to other populations. Data is self-reported and may be biased. Use for project: Even in patients with conditions that require sun-protection and know to avoid the sun, educational and behavioral counseling is still needed.

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To characterize skin cancer prevention and education needs in uninsured, minority, and immigrant communities in South Florida (Jacobsen et al., 2016).	<p>Non-experimental; descriptive survey</p> <p>Key Variables: Demographics: Age, sex, occupation, educational level Knowledge: skin cancer risk, knowledge and use of sun-protective behaviors, barriers to protective behaviors</p>	<p>Setting: Large, free medical clinic in Florida</p> <p>Convenience sample of 206 participants</p> <p>Inclusion criteria: uninsured and living at least 200% below federal poverty levels, adults, had to understand English, Spanish, or Haitian Creole language</p> <p>Most participants were women (75%), majority from Central America (37.9%) with primary level of education (36.3%). Mean age was 43 years old</p>	<p>23-question survey assessing their skin cancer risk perception, knowledge, sun protective behaviors and barriers, and desirable outreach methods</p> <p>Survey questions adapted to sixth-grade level or below</p>	<p>75% of respondents were women who usually worked indoors. 24.5% had never heard of skin cancer or melanoma. 44.3% had never conducted a self-skin examination. 20.7% believed that people with dark skin cannot get skin cancer. 75.7% had “low/inconsistent” sun protective behaviors. Barriers to sun-protective behaviors were “using sun protection is too hot” (39.3%) and “I forget” (37.7%). 87.9% wanted to learn more about how to prevent skin cancer. Watching a video (37.3%) and text messaging (30.8%) were identified as the most popular outreach methods.</p>	<p>Conclusion: Belief is present that dark skinned individuals are protected from skin cancer. Barriers to skin cancer prevention are lack of knowledge. Video and text messaging may be a source to provide information.</p> <p>Limitations: Study mainly included female participants. Participants included lower income and uninsured patients and may not represent other populations at risk.</p> <p>Useful for project: Most patients with melasma are darker-skinned and may believe they do not need sunscreen or protection</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
The purpose of this study was to test the efficacy of a web-based melanoma prevention intervention in melanoma survivors (Bowen et al., 2015).	<p>Experimental; Randomized study design</p> <p>Key Variables: Family unit, family communication, internet capability. Web-based intervention was interactive with participants and among family members</p> <p>Inclusion criteria: family must have a melanoma survivor (diagnosed between 4/1/98 and 10/1/01), a 1st degree relative, and a parent). All participants must be at least 18 years old and have access to the internet.</p>	<p>311 families recruited through population-based registry (Northwest Cancer Genetic Network or the Cancer Surveillance System) and assessed through a phone survey, then randomized into an immediate intervention or delayed comparison group. Intervention group families received access to the study website for 1 year. Enrolled families completed a survey 1 year later and that is when comparison families had access to the website.</p>	<p>Families randomized into the intervention group or to serve as control group. Intervention was web-based that focused on increasing family communication and exchange of risk information</p> <p>Every 3 months, a new email would go out to prompt the family to check the website for new information</p> <p>Outcome measurements included skin self-examinations (at least once every 2 months), sun-protective behaviors (seeking shade, wearing protective clothing, using sunscreen), and seeking provider screenings.</p>	<p>Cases signed onto website 1.9 times during intervention period. 4% did not visit at all. Average pages per use was 8.4. Most frequently visited pages were risk information (96%), protecting skin from sun (78%), and talking to family and providers (64% and 61%).</p> <p>Intervention survivors improved skin self-examination and sun protective behaviors significantly compared to comparison survivors. Higher levels of perceived risk and cancer worry were associated with increased intervention effect. Survivors that felt closeness to family were more likely to increase sun protective behaviors.</p>	<p>Conclusions: Use of web-based interventions for behavioral change are supported.</p> <p>Limitations: Participants were almost all Caucasian, slightly more likely to be female than male, mostly of moderate income and education, and mostly of lower stage of melanoma. May not represent other populations.</p> <p>Useful for project: This study uses significant others as a means for influencing sun protective behaviors (consistent with HPM) and can be applied to melasma patients.</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To evaluate use of a mobile application that provided sun protection advice to reduce the risk of skin cancer (Buller et al., 2015).	Randomized pretest-posttest controlled design, potential participants randomized into treatment group or control group Key variables: Treatment group intervention: Solar Cell mobile app. 10 weeks post recruitment, all participants received invitation to posttest. Key demographics: Inclusion criteria: Non-Hispanic or Hispanic white, 18 years of age or older, U.S. resident. Android phones only.	Sample recruited from Knowledge Panel (survey panel representative of the U.S. adult population) and then screened on smart phone ownership. Recruited July 10-23, 2012 454 participants included in study: 222 in treatment group, 232 in control group Ages ranged from 18 to 80 years, equally divided on gender. 24.2% had high-risk skin phenotypes and nearly 1/3 had been diagnosed with skin cancer. Participants were well-educated	Solar Cell Mobile App: provided personalized sun protection advice based on skin phenotype, clothing coverage, use of sunscreen/spf, and medications that increase sun sensitivity. Also provided advice on risk of sunburn, time until reapplication, recommended sun protection practices, and current forecasted UV index.	Only 125 (41%) of the treatment group used the app at least once after installation. Treatment group reported using shade more than controls. Treatment group users used sunscreen less than controls.	Conclusions: Smart phone applications may help with disease prevention in those that engage in them proactively. Despite disappointing results, the Solar Cell app may still benefit adults with high risk skin types that spend a lot of time outdoors. Limitations: Not generalizable to other racial/ethnic groups. Only useful for those that use the app consistently, many participants in treatment group did not use the app. Useful for project: Melasma patients may be more driven to engage in sun-protective behaviors due the condition mainly affecting the face and being a cosmetic concern. A phone application may be very successful in this motivated group.

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To examine sun protection behaviors and their association with self-efficacy, susceptibility, and skin cancer awareness in low-income primary care patients (Kamimura et al., 2015).	<p>Non-experimental; Descriptive cross-sectional study</p> <p>Key Variables: Amount of sun exposure, sunscreen use, wearing protective clothing, self-efficacy, skin cancer susceptibility/awareness, demographic details (age, gender, race, education level, employment status, marital status, country of origin, years in US, years as a patient of the clinic)</p>	<p>Uninsured primary care patients utilizing a free clinic in the Intermountain West (Utah) completed a self-administered survey in May and June 2015.</p> <p>Participants divided into three groups: US born English speakers, non-US born English speakers, and Spanish speakers</p> <p>551 participants of a convenience sample (164 US born English speakers, 129 non-US born English speakers, and 258 Spanish speakers). Average age was 44.37 years. 66.2% of the participants were women, 62.3% self-identified as Hispanic, Latino, or Latina, 25% were white. 44.1% reported having some college</p>	<p>Five sun protection related questions were extracted from the Health Information National Trends Survey (used in previous research). Self-efficacy was measured by the General Self-Efficacy Scale (Cronbach's alpha for this study population was 0.905). Skin cancer susceptibility and awareness were measured by the scale based on the Health Belief Model (Cronbach's alpha for this study population was 0.825 for the susceptibility subscale and 0.921 for the awareness subscale).</p>	<p>Common Sun Protective Behaviors: the most common sun protective behavior in all groups was wearing long pants and shirts with sleeves. Using sunscreen was the least common. Spanish speakers were more likely to wear a hat and likely to wear shirts with sleeves compared to other groups. Spanish speakers had the highest levels of self-efficacy and reported higher levels of susceptibility, but lower levels of awareness than other groups.</p> <p>Predictors of Sun-Protective Behaviors: ↑ levels of self-efficacy were associated with ↑ levels of sunscreen use. ↑ levels of awareness were associated with ↑ levels of using sunscreen and shade/umbrella and of wearing a hat and shirts with sleeves. Female participants were more likely to use sunscreen (p<0.01) and shade/umbrella (p<0.05),</p>	<p>Conclusions: Sunscreen use is the most common sun protective behaviors in the general US population, yet in this study, sunscreen was the least common behavior used. Spanish speakers have lower levels of skin cancer awareness compared to US born and non-US born English speakers. Low-income primary care patients (particularly Spanish-speaking) can benefit from increased awareness of skin cancer and education on low-cost sun protection methods. Gender-specific sun protection education may provide additional awareness</p> <p>Limitations: Recall, reporter bias. Patients who were not literate in either English or Spanish were not</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
		<p>or higher levels of education. US born English speakers had higher numbers of some college or higher levels of education (62.8%) compared with non-US born English speakers (49.6%) and Spanish speakers (29.5%).</p>		<p>but were less likely to wear a hat ($p < 0.01$) and shirts with sleeves ($p < 0.05$) compared to male participants.</p>	<p>included. May not represent the greater US population. Participants were at the clinic for other reasons and may not be interested in survey at the time.</p> <p>Useful for project: Melasma disproportionately affects patients with darker skin tones and many people in my clinic identify as Hispanic and Latina and are Spanish-speaking predominant. Providing melasma education materials in Spanish may benefit these patients.</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To evaluate the impact of tailored print material on skin cancer prevention behaviors, skin self-examinations, and provider skin examinations among adults at moderate to high risk of skin cancer (Glanz et al., 2014)	<p>Randomized controlled trial comparing effects of mailed tailored print materials vs generic print materials</p> <p>Key variables: knowledge, beliefs, and attitudes about skin cancer, sun exposure and protection habits, social norms about sun protection, and detection behaviors</p>	<p>Outpatient health practice associated with the University of Pennsylvania Health System between May and June 2011.</p> <p>Convenience sampling of primary care patients at moderate to high risk for skin cancer were recruited from waiting room area and randomized into 1 of 2 groups.</p> <p>Inclusion criteria: Caucasian adults at moderate or high risk for skin cancer. Exclusion criteria: previous history of melanoma or would be out of town for more than 3 consecutive weeks</p>	<p>Treatment group received three tailored mailings including a personalized risk assessment, recommendations for sun protection and skin cancer detection, and sun safety reminders.</p> <p>Control group received three mailings with pamphlets containing standard skin cancer detection and prevention recommendations.</p>	<p>192 Participants completed the study.</p> <p>Relative to generic communications, tailored risk communications resulted in improved adherence to six skin cancer protective behaviors :overall sun protection behavior (P = 0.025); sunscreen use (P = 0.026); use of sunglasses (P = 0.011); sunburns in the past three months (P = 0.033); recency of last skin self-exam (P = 0.017); and frequency of skin exams by health care provider (P = 0.016).</p>	<p>Conclusion: Tailored risk communications for adults at moderate or high risk for skin cancer were more effective at improving adherence to sun-protective behaviors than generic print communications.</p> <p>Limitations: 100% of participants were Caucasian and nearly ¾ were female which is not generalizable to other populations.</p> <p>Useful for project: Individually-tailored educational materials may increase sun-protective behaviors in patients with melasma.</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To reduce risk of skin cancer in Adult Hispanics (Hernandez et al., 2014).	<p>Quasi-experimental; pretest and posttest and semi-structured interviews.</p> <p>Key Variables: sun-protection education, awareness, risk perception</p>	Convenience sample recruited from local beauty salons in primarily Hispanic neighborhoods	<p>Pre-intervention questionnaire given assessed subjects general knowledge and sunscreen use. 2 Spanish-language films were shown.</p> <p>Post test questionnaire administered after film</p>	80 participants in ages ranging from 19-75 years. 54 of 80 believed fair-skinned Hispanic people were at risk for skin cancer, 44 of 80 also believed dark-skinned Hispanics were at risk. These numbers increased to 72 and 69 after video intervention.	<p>Conclusion: Video-based public health educational programs can benefit Hispanic population regarding sun-protection and skin cancer risk</p> <p>Limitations: Mainly Hispanic female participants, may not be generalizable to other ethnicities and males.</p> <p>Useful for project: Even a brief educational intervention could be useful for sun-protection education.</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To offer Sun Solutions intervention to operating engineers to decrease sun exposure and risk of skin cancer (Lee et al., 2014).	<p>Quasi-experimental pretest-posttest intervention study that was part of a larger RCT</p> <p>Key variables: Education, mailed sunscreen, text message reminders HBM constructs also investigated.</p>	<p>232 participants enrolled.</p> <p>Site: Howell, Michigan</p>	<p>30-minute PowerPoint presentation administered by research nurse. Content consisted of sun-protective practices of current operating engineers who participated in last survey. Also discussed risk of cancer, sunburn, UV types. Education on sun protection methods including protective clothing, seeking shade, wearing sunscreen. How to apply sunscreen also discussed.</p>	<p>82% of participants worked outside between 10am and 3pm. 81.4% reported more than one sunburn in past year. 70% sometimes or never used sunscreen.</p> <p>Sun-protective behaviors: after intervention, improved self-efficacy and perceived benefits.</p>	<p>Conclusion: After 30-minute PowerPoint, 84% expressed they intended to use sunscreen in the future.</p> <p>Limitations: Mainly white males in study, may not be generalizable to other populations.</p> <p>Useful for project: Even a brief educational intervention could be useful for sun-protection education.</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To determine if women consider handheld umbrellas (HUs) a socially acceptable form of sun protection and to determine predictors of HU use and reasons for not using HU (McMichael et al., 2014).	<p>Cross-sectional survey of 382 women</p> <p>Key variables: history of HU use for sun-protection, social acceptability of HU use, previous sun-protective behaviors</p>	<p>Surveys given in Atlanta to community and university-affiliated women 18 years and older between 8/13/11-8/3/12</p> <p>Exclusion criteria: male sex, < 18 yrs old, inability to read</p>	<p>3-part survey:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Asked if they used HU for sun protection in last year and rate isf socially acceptable 2. Demographic questions and skin characterizing questions. Sun-protective behaviors were also assessed. 3. Rate how socially acceptable HU is for sun protection in the future 	<p>Mean age=31 years. 66% were young women ages 18-29 years. 78% completed at least some college. HU users were older and more educated.</p> <p>12% used HU for sun protection in past year (ages ranged from 22 to 69 years old). Top 3 reasons for using were: avoiding wrinkles, convenient way to protect skin, at risk for skin cancer. Top 3 reasons for not using: like hands free, not convenient, never thought about using one before.</p> <p>71% of non-HU users stated they would be more likely to use HU if more people in the US used them.</p>	<p>Conclusions: AAD and other organizations promote sunscreen, shade seeking, and sun-protective clothing without promoting HU use. More people would use HU if they see others doing it.</p> <p>Limitations: majority of participants identified as white and may not represent overall population. Recall bias, social desirability bias, selection bias.</p> <p>Useful for project: Melasma patients would benefit from all types of sun-protective behaviors. Hus should also be encouraged.</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To evaluate patients' awareness of importance of sun protection while in vehicles, to assess patients' perceptions and compliance with sun-protective measures, and to detect laterality in MM and NMSC (Kim, Chabra I., Chabra P., & Jones, 2013).	<p>Non-experimental; Retrospective descriptive study</p> <p>Key variables and demographics: Driving habits, frequency of sunscreen use while in vehicle, impressions about sun protection, recreational activities, sunscreen use, medical history, family history of skin cancer, skin type, site of skin cancer, Key demographics: age, gender, personal and family history of skin cancer</p>	675 surveys were mailed to patients seen at a Mohs micrographic surgery clinic in Pittsburg, Pennsylvania and 225 surveys were received. Median age was 68 years, 56% female and 44% male. 89% identified as fair skinned (skin types I-III) and 90% had a history of at least 1 type of skin cancer. 30 patients had a MM, 102 had at least 1 NMSC, and 12 had both MM and NMSC.	A self-administered survey was mailed to patients asking about their driving habits (driver or passenger, hours driving, open or closed windows, tinted windows, sunscreen use while in vehicle) and medical history (skin type, previous and family history of skin cancers) and sunscreen use.	<p>Majority of respondents felt they did not need sunscreen while driving if the windows were closed or open. Of those with a personal history of skin cancer, 53.4% believed they needed sunscreen while driving with windows open compared to 18.2% of those without a history of skin cancer ($p < 0.01$). Fewer patients reported using sunscreen while in a vehicle compared with general daily sunscreen use (52% vs 27%, $p < 0.05$). Those who believed they were protected from sun while in a vehicle were less likely to use sunscreen (12% vs 46%, $p < 0.05$).</p> <p>Respondents who were female and had a family history of MM were more likely to use sunscreen in a vehicle.</p> <p>NMSC occurred more often on the left side of</p>	<p>Conclusions: The majority of patients in this study did not think they needed to use sunscreen while driving. Use of sunscreen and tinted windows may reduce left-sided NMCS.</p> <p>Limitations Selection bias- participants already had a history of skin cancer and most patients were older (average age was 67.5 years) therefore findings may not be generalizable to other populations. Questionnaire was self-administered and may have included recall bias and patients may have answered in a socially desirable way</p> <p>Useful for project: in the clinic, melasma appears to be worse on the left-side of patients, most notably</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
				<p>the body and MM occurred more often on the right. Patients who never had tinted windows had more left-sided NMSC (86% vs 42%, $p < 0.05$). Patients with right-sided NMSC were more likely to have tinted windows than left-sided NMSC (86% vs 39%, $p < 0.01$).</p>	<p>their cheeks and forehead. Melasma patients may not realize they need sunscreen while driving. It would be interesting to assess sunscreen use while driving in this population.</p>

Purpose, (Author(s), year)	Design and Key Variables	Sample and Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Limitations & Notes
To quantify changes in sunscreen use before and after transplantation (Mihalís et al., 2013)	Cross-sectional, retrospective survey Key variables: increased risk of skin cancer from immunosuppressed status, sunscreen, sun avoidance behavior	National sample of 198 organ transplant recipients in the U.S. from 2004-2008 Inclusion criteria: no prior history of skin cancer	Sunscreen use before and after transplantation. Frequency of sunscreen use and sun exposure obtained through self-report on Likert scales ranging from never to always	Sex, skin typing, receiving advice to avoid sun from provider, pre-transplantation sunscreen use significantly associated with frequency of post-transplantation sunscreen use Pretransplantation sun exposure, advice to avoid sun, Pretransplantation sunscreen use significantly associated with sun avoidance post-transplantation	Conclusion: Previous behavior and clinician advice are associated with sun-protective behaviors Limitations: Study not characterized by region or UV radiation exposure. Useful for project: Even patients at increased risk need additional advice for sun-protective behaviors

Note. HBM = Health Belief Model, HU=Handheld Umbrella, PIH = Postinflammatory Hyperpigmentation, MM = Malignant Melanoma, MASI = Melasma Area and Severity Index, NHIS = National Health Interview Survey, NMSC = Non Melanoma Skin Cancer, SPF = Sun Protection Factor, TTM = Transtheoretical Model, UVA = Ultraviolet A, UVB = Ultraviolet B

APPENDIX C

STUDY INFORMATION SHEET

Laura Conahan is a candidate in the Doctor of Nursing Practice Program at California State University, Fullerton. She has chosen to do her research on sun-protective behaviors of adult patients with melasma. If you are an adult diagnosed with melasma and are willing to participate, it would require that you read and sign an informed consent and complete a demographic questionnaire and sun-protection survey. If you do not meet the criteria or do not want to be in the study, please do not sign the consent and do not fill out the other forms. Simply return all documents unsigned and blank to the front office staff.

If you chose to participate in this study and you will have read and signed the informed consent. At the end of the informed consent, you will be asked if you are willing to participate in a focus group interview that will be scheduled at a later date and time. The purpose of the interview is to gain understanding about your lived experience of having melasma and engaging in sun-protection. You do not have to be interviewed to be involved in the study. You can also choose to be interviewed independently.

After signing the informed consent, next complete the demographic questionnaire and sun-protection survey. Do not put your name or anything that could identify you on these papers. Demographic information collected will include, gender, ethnicity, marital status, highest educational level attained, and questions related to melasma and sun-protection. You will need approximately 10 minutes to fill out the consent form, demographic survey, and sun-protection survey, but can take more time if needed. You may also choose to fill out this information at home and return by mail, in which case the front desk staff will provide you with a self-addressed stamped envelope. When you have completed the consent form, demographic questionnaire, and sun-protection survey, please return them to the front desk staff. If you did not fill out a consent, do not meet criteria, or do not want to be included in the study, please write “do not use” on the top of your paper and your data will not be used, or you may just leave the documents blank.

You will not receive scores from the sun-protection survey because of confidentiality, but you will be given details as to where to access this exact scale online, so that you can get your score if you choose to. There is no financial payment for your participation in the study. Participation is strictly voluntary. There will be no repercussions for not participating. If at any time during this study you change your mind and decide not to participate, that is perfectly acceptable. Just leave the papers blank or partially filled if you have already started and the data will not be used. Another option would be to write “do not use” on either sheet of paper; your wishes will be respected. Please return all documentation to the front office staff.

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Laura Conahan by phone at 714-655-9451 or by email at lconahan@csu.fullerton.edu. You may also contact the lead study advisor, Dr. Sue Robertson, by phone at 657-278-3567 or by email at srobertson@fullerton.edu. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719, or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu. I would like to thank you for being a part of my research.

-Laura Conahan, Nurse Practitioner, Researcher

APPENDIX D**CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY FULLERTON RESEARCH
STUDY CONSENT FORM**

Study Title: Sun-Protective Behaviors in Patients with Melasma

Protocol Number: HSR-18-19-57

Researchers: Laura Conahan, doctoral student; Dr. Sue Robertson and Dr. Karla Parsons, Nursing Professors and Study Advisors

You are being asked to take part in a research study carried out by Laura Conahan, FNP-C, MSN, Sue Robertson, RN, PhD, and Karla Parsons, FNP-BC, DNP. This consent form explains the research study and your part in it if you decide to join the study. Please read the form carefully, taking as much time as you need. Ask the researcher to explain anything you don't understand. You can decide not to join the study. If you join the study, you can change your mind later and leave the study at any time. There will be no penalty or loss of services or benefits if you decide to not take part in the study.

What is this study about?

This research study is being conducted to identify barriers to sun-protective behaviors in patients with melasma. The results of this study will be used to determine ways to better provide care for this health issue. You are being asked to take part in this study because you are a patient over the age of 18 years that has been diagnosed with melasma. Taking part in the study will take about 10 minutes. You cannot take part in this study if you are under 18 years of age or if you do not have a diagnosis of melasma.

What will I be asked to do if I am in this study?

If you take part in the study, you will be asked to:

1. Carefully read the consent form stating that you meet all of the requirements for this study (that you are 18-years-old or older and have melasma) and that you understand the risks and benefits of participating in this study. If you agree to participate, sign the last page of this consent form.
2. Carefully read and follow the directions on the top page of the demographic questionnaire and Sun Exposure and Protection Index (SEPI) survey. Approximately 10 minutes will be required to complete all forms, but you can take more time if needed. You may also fill out this information at home and return to us by mail. Ask the front desk staff for a self-addressed stamped envelope if you would like to return by mail.

3. After signing the consent form and completing the demographic questionnaire and SEPI survey, return all three documents to the front desk staff.
4. At the end of the consent form, you will be asked if you are willing to participate in a focus group (when multiple participants meet together to discuss a topic). The purpose of the focus group will be to discuss how you were diagnosed with melasma, how melasma has impacted your life (especially with outdoor activities), and to understand how you practice sun-protective behaviors.
 - a. You may also have the option of having an individual interview instead of the focus group if you feel uncomfortable in a group setting.
 - b. The focus group or interview will be audio-recorded for the purposes of transcribing only.
 - c. You do not have to be interviewed to participate in this study. It is acceptable to just complete the consent form, demographic questionnaire, and SEPI survey.
 - d. The focus group (or individual interview) will be scheduled at a later date and the front desk staff will contact you by phone regarding the date and time. The focus group or individual interview may take 30 minutes, but can be longer depending on the size of the group.

Are there any benefits to me if I am in this study?

There are no direct benefits for participating in this study. You may, however, gain awareness about the importance of sun-protective behaviors for patients with melasma. Other patients may benefit from this study, as it may fill in gaps in the knowledge about sun-protective behaviors in melasma patients. In addition, this study may lead to the development of more appropriate patient education materials.

Are there any risks to me if I am in this study?

There are minimal risks related to demographic questionnaires and self-reported surveys. There may be a potential risk of loss of privacy from being in the same area as other participants when filling out the questionnaire and survey. There are minimal risks related to focus group or individual interviews. There may be a potential risk of loss of privacy during the focus group. When participating in a focus group, the researcher cannot guarantee that the other participants will not repeat concepts heard outside of the focus group setting. If this is a concern, you may have an individual interview as an alternative to the focus group. You may experience mild anxiety while answering the questionnaire and survey and during the focus group or interview if you are reminded of an unpleasant memory related to the subject matter. Please let us know if this occurs.

The time it takes to complete the questionnaire, survey, and interview may be inconvenient and can be rescheduled for a more convenient time.

Will my information be kept anonymous or confidential?

Information obtained in this study that can be identified with you will remain confidential to the full extent allowed by law. Study results will only be reported in aggregate (results of all patients together). Your demographic questionnaire, SEPI survey, and focus group or interview responses will remain confidential. Data collected will be kept in a locked file cabinet and on a password protected computer in the researcher's home and in the faculty offices at CSUF. Only the researcher and study advisors (Dr. Robertson and Dr. Parsons) will have access to the data. At the end of the study/publication, data will be destroyed with the exception of qualitative transcripts which will be retained for five years for possible secondary analysis. No legal ramifications can be taken by answering the demographic questionnaire, SEPI survey, and focus group or individual interview questions. All information collected is for research and educational purposes only. Results of this project may be published, but no names or identifying information will be included for publication.

Are there any costs or payments for being in this study?

There will be no costs to you for taking part in this study. You will not receive money or other form of compensation for taking part in this study.

Who can I talk to if I have questions?

If you have questions about this study or the information in this form, please contact the researcher Laura Conahan by phone at 714-655-9451 or by email at ljconahan@csu.fullerton.edu. You may also contact the lead study advisor, Dr. Sue Robertson, by phone at 657-278-3567 or by email at srobertson@fullerton.edu. If you have questions about your rights as a research participant, or would like to report a concern or complaint about this study, please contact the Institutional Review Board at (657) 278-7719, or e-mail irb@fullerton.edu

What are my rights as a research study volunteer?

Your participation in this research study is completely voluntary. You may choose not to be a part of this study. There will be no penalty to you if you choose not to take part. You may choose not to answer specific questions or to stop participating at any time.

What does my signature on this consent form mean?

Your signature on this form means that:

- You understand the information given to you in this form
- You have been able to ask the researcher questions and state any concerns
- The researcher has responded to your questions and concerns

- You believe you understand the research study and the potential benefits and risks that are involved.

Statement of Consent

I have carefully read and/or I have had the terms used in this consent form and their significance explained to me. By signing below, I agree that I am at least 18 years of age and agree to participate in this project. You will be given a copy of this signed and dated consent form to keep.

Name of Participant (please print) _____

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

Signature of Investigator _____ Date _____

At a later date, a focus group or individual interview will be scheduled with the purpose of understanding the lived experience of sun-protective behaviors in patients with melasma. Front office staff at Forever Ageless Inc. will contact you regarding a date and time.

I am interested in participating in a focus group or individual interview (please check yes or no):

_____ yes

_____ no

Your signature below indicates that you are giving permission to audio-record your responses during the focus group or individual interview.

Signature of Participant _____ Date _____

APPENDIX E
DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONNAIRE

Do not write your name on this survey. Please check as appropriate

1. What is your age?
 - 18-24 years
 - 25-34 years
 - 35-44 years
 - 45-54 years
 - 55-64 years
 - 65+ years

2. What is your gender?
 - Female
 - Male
 - Other (please specify: _____)
 - Prefer not to state

3. What is your marital status?
 - Single
 - Married
 - Divorced/Separated
 - Widowed
 - Prefer not to state

4. What is your highest level of education completed?
 - Did not finish high school
 - High School or GED
 - Some college/did not finish degree
 - Associate Degree/ Technical or Trade School
 - Bachelor's Degree
 - Graduate Degree
 - Prefer not to state

5. Do you have health insurance?
 - Yes
 - No
 - Prefer not to state

6. What is your ethnicity?
 - African American/Black
 - Asian/Pacific Islander
 - Caucasian/White
 - Hispanic/Latino

- Indian
- Middle Eastern
- Native American/American Indian
- Other (please specify: _____)
- Prefer not to state

7. What is your natural hair color?

- Black
- Brown
- Blonde
- Red

8. What is your natural eye color?

- Brown
- Hazel
- Green
- Blue/Gray

9. How does your skin react if you were in the sun for more than 1 hour without sun-protection?

- Always burns easily, never tans
- Always burns easily, tans slightly
- Burns moderately, tans gradually
- Burns minimally, tans moderately
- Rarely burns, tans profusely
- Never burns, tans profusely

10. How many years have you had melasma?

- < 1 year
- 1-2 years
- 3-4 years
- 5-6 years
- 7 or more years

11. How often do you think about your melasma?

- Never
- Rarely
- Occasionally
- Often
- Always

12. Does sun exposure make your melasma (the darker color of your skin) worse?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

13. Do you use sunscreen?

No

Yes

If yes:

Is your sunscreen broad spectrum?

yes

no

unsure

What is the SPF of your sunscreen?

< 15

15-29

30-49

50+

unsure

After first application of sunscreen, how often do you reapply?

every 2 hours

every 3-5 hours

every 6-8 hours

do not reapply

APPENDIX F

SUN EXPOSURE AND PROTECTION INDEX SURVEY

Sun Exposure and Protection Index (SEPI)

- Part I -

1. How often do you sunbathe with the intention to get tanned?	0 <input type="checkbox"/> Never 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Always
2. How many times have you been sunburnt (redness and smarting pain) during the last 12 months?	0 <input type="checkbox"/> None 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 1-2 times 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 3-5 times 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 6-10 times 4 <input type="checkbox"/> More than 10 times
3. How long do you usually stay in the sun (on average), between 11 am and 3 pm, on a typical day-off?	0 <input type="checkbox"/> < 30 min 1 <input type="checkbox"/> 30 min – 1 hour 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 1-2 hours 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 2-3 hours 4 <input type="checkbox"/> > 3 hours
4. How often do you take a holiday with the intention of spending more time in the sun?	0 <input type="checkbox"/> Never 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 2 <input type="checkbox"/> 1-2 weeks a year 3 <input type="checkbox"/> 3-5 weeks a year 4 <input type="checkbox"/> > 5 weeks a year
5. When in the sun, how often do you use sunscreens?	0 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Never
6. When in the sun, how often do you use covering clothes for sun protection?	0 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Never
7. When in the sun, how often do you use a sun hat or cap for sun protection?	0 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Never
8. How often do you stay indoors or in the shade in order to protect yourself from the sun?	0 <input type="checkbox"/> Always 1 <input type="checkbox"/> Often 2 <input type="checkbox"/> Occasionally 3 <input type="checkbox"/> Seldom 4 <input type="checkbox"/> Never

– Part II –

Choose for each item which statement is most consistent with your own state:

1. Sunbathing: 4 I have never thought of giving up sunbathing.
 3 I could think of giving up sunbathing.
 2 I intend to give up sunbathing.
 1 I have recently given up sunbathing .
 0 I have for a long time avoided sunbathing
2. Sunscreens: 4 I have never thought of using sunscreens.
 3 I could think of using sunscreens.
 2 I intend to start using sunscreens.
 1 I have started to use sunscreens.
 0 I have for a long time used sunscreens.
3. Covering clothes: 4 I have never thought of using covering clothes for sun protection.
 3 I could think of using covering clothes for sun protection.
 2 I intend to start using covering clothes for sun protection.
 1 I have started to use covering clothes for sun protection.
 0 I have for a long time used covering clothes for sun protection.
4. Sun hat or cap: 4 I have never thought of using a sun hat or cap for sun protection.
 3 I could think of using a sun hat or cap for sun protection.
 2 I intend to start using a sun hat or cap for sun protection.
 1 I have started to use a sun hat or cap for sun protection.
 0 I have for a long time used a sun hat or cap for sun protection.
5. The shade: 4 I have never thought of trying to stay in the shade during the hours of strongest sun light.
 3 I could think of trying to stay in the shade during the hours of strongest sun light.
 2 I intend to start trying to stay in the shade during the hours of strongest sun light.
 1 I have started trying to stay in the shade during the hours of strongest sun light.
 0 I have for a long time tried to stay in the shade during the hours of strongest sun light.

– Scoring instructions –

SEPI part I: For each question, the given response score (0-4 p), should be added together in a total score (0-32 p), reflecting *increasing UV risk exposure*.

SEPI part II: For each question, the given response score (0-4 p), should be added together in a total score (0-20 p), reflecting *decreasing propensity to increase sun protection*.

SEPI - part I
score:

SEPI - part
score:

APPENDIX G

FOCUS GROUP SCRIPT AND INTERVIEW GUIDE

Introduction: Thank you for taking the time to participate in this interview. I will ask you questions to better understand your life experiences with melasma. Participating in this interview will not affect patient care. Choosing to not answer a question or stopping the interview early will not affect patient care. This interview will be audio-recorded as described in the consent form. To protect confidentiality, I will not transcribe your name or other personal identifiable information. I will use a code number to identify you in the transcript. Do you have any questions before we begin?

1. Tell me what it is like living with melasma.
2. Tell me about how you protect yourself from the sun.
 - a. How is sun related to melasma?
 - b. How does sunscreen protect you?
 - c. How often do you re-apply sunscreen?
 - d. Aside from sunscreen, what other methods do you use to protect yourself?
 - e. Is there anything that gets in the way of you protecting yourself from the sun?
 - i. Follow-up question if problem is forgetfulness- what would help you remember to protect yourself?
 - ii. Follow-up question if problem is inconvenience- what would make using sunscreen or other methods more convenient to use?
3. What are activities that you enjoy doing while outside during the day?
 - a. Do you feel that melasma has interfered or limited you from doing these activities or being outside during the day? Please give examples.
4. How has melasma positively or negatively impacted your life? Please give examples.
 - a. Financial, physical, emotional impact?
 - b. Has it affected your relationships in any way? Taken time away?
5. Are there any other questions that you can think of that I should ask the next person I interview to get a better understanding of melasma and how it relates to sun-protection?

APPENDIX H

QUALITATIVE THEME AND SUB-THEMES

Table H1

Theme and Sub-Themes with Supportive Quotes

Living with Melasma	Mine is from sun exposure, I can guarantee that 100%. You know so now that's the issue . . . I did permanent damage to myself. I understand that. Not happy with myself about it, but it is what it is . . . I did things wrong a long time ago, but now the problem is that it's irreversible and it's now here and I've got to deal with it.
Sun-Protective Behaviors	I don't remember to reapply. How do you do that with makeup on? That is still challenging for me. Like with foundation and blush, I don't see how people do that.
Managing Melasma	I think for me it's more of a burden than anything else just because I have never really, until I had kids, had much of a skin issue. I've never really had to wear makeup, I felt, and so now it's something I feel like I have to cover up because it doesn't look nice. Yeah, it's just been a burden for me. It's something that's made me self-conscious where I haven't had to be self-conscious before.